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AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

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Deliverable 8.3

Dissemination and Communication Activities Report (v2)

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Disclaimer

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¹ Due to the nature of this deliverable, all PLIADES partners have provided feedback and revisions.

Executive Summary

This report outlines the dissemination and communication work carried out in the PLIADES project from the start of the project (January 2024) through to June 2025 (M1-M18). It builds on the activities presented in the first report (D8.2), extending the timeline and adding updates on progress made over the past six months.

The consortium has continued to build visibility around the project by updating and expanding its communication materials, maintaining an active presence on the website and social media, publishing newsletters, and participating in key European events. Over this period, we have seen solid growth in our online audience, improved engagement metrics, and increased awareness of PLIADES across various communities.

Some highlights from this period include the publication of the third project newsletter, the release of a new promotional video, and a strong presence at high-level conferences such as ERF 2025 and Data Week 2025. The project has also maintained close collaboration with other Horizon Europe projects, especially within the Data Space Cluster, to align messages and share knowledge.

The deliverable also includes updated KPIs and analytics that show good progress across the board. Lastly, it touches on the ongoing work related to the training activities that will be further developed in the upcoming months.

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List of Terms and Definitions

Table 1 Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CIA principles	Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability principles
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CMC	Connected Motorcycle Consortium
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EBDVF	European Big Data Value Forum
ECS	European Convergence Summit
ERF	European Robotics Forum
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIT	Hellenic Institute of Transport
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDS RAM	International Data Spaces Reference Architecture Model
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OEMs	Original Equipment Manufacturers
RTOs	Research and Technology Organisations
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SMEs	Small and Medium-Sized enterprises
TIF	Thessaloniki International Fair
TTG	Technology Thematic Group
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the Deliverable

This deliverable provides an overview of all dissemination and communication activities carried out in the PLIADES project during its first 18 months (January 2024 - June 2025). It builds upon D8.2 – “Dissemination and Communication Activities Report (v1)”, which detailed the actions undertaken during the first year (submitted in M12), and includes all updates, new actions and measurable progress achieved over the subsequent six-month period.

The focus remains on increasing visibility around the project, keeping stakeholders engaged, and supporting the broader uptake of results through targeted communication. Activities presented in this report include updates to the website, social media performance, newsletters, short videos, event participation and published articles or papers. It also covers how the project has worked with other related initiatives, particularly those in the Data Space Cluster.

The goal of this report is not just to document what has been done, but also to track how well the project’s outreach efforts are working through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and feedback, and to support future exploitation and training actions by laying a strong communication foundation.

1.2 Relation to other Activities and Deliverables

The dissemination and communication activities in D8.2 are aligned with other key deliverables and activities within the PLIADES project to ensure consistency and effectiveness. Below are the key connections:

- D8.1 – “Dissemination and Communication Plan”: The activities in D8.2 follow the strategy, objectives, and KPIs set in D8.1, ensuring that dissemination efforts remain focused and aligned with the project’s goals.
- Exploitation Strategy (D8.3 – “Dissemination and Communication Activities Report (v2)”, D8.4 – “Dissemination and Communication Activities Report (v3)”): Dissemination in D8.2 helps pave the way for future exploitation by raising awareness of Key Exploitable Results (KERs). These efforts will support the exploitation pathways to be defined in D8.3 and D8.4, thereby increasing visibility and interest in project outcomes.
- Online Presence (website, social media, newsletters): The project’s website, social media, and newsletters are key tools for promoting events, publications, and KERs. D8.2 tracks the effectiveness of these channels, ensuring continuous improvement.
- Contributions from Other Work Packages (WPs): As the project progresses and more results become available, dissemination activities will draw on content from WPs 3, 4, 6, and 7. This will include technical outputs from pilots, privacy-preserving methods, and Key Exploitable Results.
- Training and Capacity Building (D8.5 – “Report on European Standardization Policy and Sustainability Landscape Analysis”, D8.6 – “Report on Exploitation Analysis and Business Plan (initial)”): Early awareness-raising activities from D8.2 support engagement for the later training deliverables (D8.5, D8.6) by building an audience and informing stakeholders about PLIADES results.

This interconnected approach strengthens the project’s outreach, ensuring all dissemination activities contribute to broader project objectives and support future exploitation.

The communication and dissemination work described in this report is closely connected to other parts of the project. It builds directly on the strategy outlined in D8.1, which defined the goals, tools and key performance indicators for PLIADES outreach activities.

It also complements the ongoing work on exploitation (D8.4) by helping to promote the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and raise awareness of project outcomes. These early communication actions support the groundwork needed for effective exploitation in the second half of the project.

In addition, this deliverable connects with results from several technical work packages (mainly WPs 3, 4, 6 and 7) and their technical outputs, which are now being shared through the project's website, social media, and events.

Lastly, this report links to Task 8.5 – “Design and implementation of training programs on security issues adopted during the implementation of the platform” on training activities. Some initial steps have already been taken, such as planning and early content development. Dissemination has played a key role in building an audience and getting future participants familiar with the project themes.

1.3 Document Structure

This deliverable is structured as follows:

Chapter 1 – Introduction: outlines the scope of the deliverable, how it relates to other project activities, and provides a brief overview of the document structure.

Chapter 2 – Dissemination Activities: presents all actions taken to promote the project, including branding, online presence, media outreach, participation in events, and publications.

Chapter 3 – Performance Indicators and Monitoring: summarises the key performance metrics defined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan and provides an update on progress made.

Chapter 4 – Training Programme Planning: provides an update on the first steps towards designing the PLIADES training programme, in line with Task 8.5.

Chapter 5 – Conclusions: offer a summary of the main findings and recommendations for the coming period.

Chapter 6 – Appendix: includes the full list of dissemination activities.

2 Dissemination Activities

2.1 Project Identity and Branding

From the early stages of the project, a clear and consistent visual identity was established to ensure a professional and recognisable presence across all communication materials. The branding package includes the official PLIADES logo, a defined colour palette, and custom templates for documents, presentations and newsletters.

These visual elements have been used throughout the project's website, social media channels, printed materials, and public presentations. The aim is to maintain a unified look and feel across all channels, which helps improve recognition and strengthen the project's visibility among stakeholders.

All of these elements were presented in detail in Deliverable D8.2, including visual examples of the logo, colour palette, and templates. The branding resources remain available to all partners and are also accessible via the Media section of the project website.

2.2 Marketing Pack and Promotional Press Kit

To support consistent communication and increase outreach, a full set of promotional materials has been developed and maintained during the project's first 18 months. These include:

- The PLIADES leaflet - a two-page brochure introducing the project, its goals, case studies, and partners. It is used at events and for general outreach.
- A3 project poster - designed for use at conferences and exhibitions, summarising the project's main messages and visual identity.
- Slide-based presentations - both a short version for general audiences and an extended version with more technical depth, tailored to workshops, conferences, or stakeholder meetings.

All materials follow the project's branding guidelines and are regularly updated to reflect new developments. The latest versions are publicly available in the Media section of the website: <https://www.pliades-project.eu/media/>

These materials are used by all partners in their dissemination efforts and help ensure the PLIADES message is presented in a clear and coordinated way.

2.3 Dissemination Channels

2.3.1 PLIADES Website

The official PLIADES website (www.pliades-project.eu) continues to serve as the main hub for all public-facing project information. It provides visitors with access to the project's objectives, use cases, partner information, news, events, public deliverables, and multimedia content. The site is regularly updated to reflect new developments and to support ongoing communication and dissemination efforts.

During the reporting period (M1-M18), the website was actively maintained with the addition of new articles, videos, and announcements. The "News" section has grown steadily, highlighting project updates and partner activities, while the "Media" section provides easy access to all visual and promotional materials.

Website Analytics (February 2024 - June 2025)

The website's performance has been monitored using analytics tools to assess its reach and user engagement.

Figure 1 Website analytics (M1-M18)

Some insights:

- Total sessions: 3,484
- Unique users: 2,600
- Website Traffic Sources

Website traffic was primarily driven by direct visits, followed by organic search and social media. According to analytics, the breakdown of traffic sources for the period February 2024 - June 2025 is as follows:

 - Direct visits: 2,391 sessions
 - Organic search: 603 sessions
 - Social media (organic): 280 sessions
 - Referral traffic: 202 sessions
- Key user acquisition channels.

Visitors arrived at the website through a range of sources. The majority came directly, followed by organic search engines and social media. The breakdown is as follows:

 - Direct traffic: 1.953 sessions
 - Organic search: 471 sessions
 - Social media (organic): 120 sessions
 - Referral traffic: 96 sessions
 - Organic video: 1 session
- Audience Geography (Top Countries)
 - Greece: 746 users
 - Spain: 519
 - United States: 271
 - Germany: 207
 - Czechia: 155
 - Italy: 100
 - Netherlands: 91
 - Ireland: 64
 - United Kingdom: 51
- Most Visited Pages

Apart from the homepage, which provides a general overview of the project, visitors most frequently accessed:

- The Partners page
- The News section
- The Media section, where dissemination material is hosted.

This shows that users are actively seeking both project background and updates on ongoing activities.

The following figures provide a visual representation of website statistics:

- Geographic distribution of users, highlighting the most active countries (e.g., Greece, Spain, United States).

Figure 2 Website analytics, geographic distribution of users

- Breakdown of the most visited pages, with high traffic observed on the landing page, Partners and News section.

Figure 3 Website analytics, breakdown of the most visited pages

Next Steps:

Looking ahead, the team will focus on:

- Publishing additional content on use cases and project results
- Promoting new videos, including videos highlighting the KERs of the PLIADES project.
- Enhancing SEO performance through better metadata and keyword targeting

The website will continue to play a key role in project communication as more outcomes and tools become available.

2.3.2 Social Media Accounts - Twitter Page, LinkedIn Page, YouTube Channel

The PLIADES project maintains an active presence on three key social media platforms: LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), and YouTube. These channels are used to share updates, promote partner activities, engage with stakeholders, and raise awareness of project results in a timely and accessible way.

Over the first 18 months of the project, we have steadily grown our audience and maintained a regular publishing rhythm. Content has included event announcements, photos, newsletter releases, publications, and video promotions.

PLIADES project performance via its social media accounts presented below:

- **LinkedIn** - <https://www.linkedin.com/company/pliades-project>
 - Followers: 220
 - Posts: 40
 - Impressions: 23,835
 - Reactions (likes, comments, shares): 986
 - Page views: 1,298

LinkedIn has been our most active platform, used for reaching professionals, researchers and industry stakeholders. It is the main channel for news, achievements, and event-related content.

- **X (formerly Twitter)** - <https://x.com/PLIADESproject>
 - Followers: 35
 - Posts: 28
 - Views: 1,300

While our audience is smaller here, we have used the platform to share real-time updates around events and to tag relevant initiatives and organisations for increased reach.

- **YouTube** - <https://www.youtube.com/@PLIADESproject>
 - Videos uploaded: 3
 - Total views: 320

The channel hosts recorded webinars and promotional videos. In May 2025, we released a short promotional video presenting the project's goals, impact and use cases, aimed at a general audience.

The image shows a screenshot of the LinkedIn profile for the PLIADES project. At the top is a banner image featuring a human hand pointing towards a blue, glowing robotic hand. Below the banner, the profile name 'PLIADES project' is displayed, along with 'Research Services · 220 followers · 51-200 employees'. There are buttons for 'Message' and 'Following'. Navigation tabs for 'Home', 'About', 'Posts', 'Jobs', and 'People' are visible. The 'Overview' section contains a paragraph about the project's focus on SoA dataspaces reference architectures and AI/Robotics. Below this is a 'Page posts' section with two recent posts. The first post, dated '1d', announces that two research papers from partner TECNALIA have been accepted for presentation. The second post, dated '3w', celebrates Claudius Laves from Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt presenting at the Data DSSC workshop. Both posts include images of the papers and a photo of Claudius Laves.

Figure 4 PLIADES LinkedIn channel

←

PLIADES project
30 posts

🔍

PLIADES project
 @PLIADESproject

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability -
 @HorizonEU funded EU project

🏢 Researcher 📍 Europe 🌐 pliaDES-project.eu 📅 Joined January 2024

32 Following 35 Followers

Posts
Replies
Highlights
Articles
Media
Likes

PLIADES project @PLIADESproject · Jun 24

📄 @PLIADESproject highlights from @tecnalia:
 2 papers accepted!

- 1 At #SpiTech2025
Data Harmonization as a Keystone for IoT-Enabled Data Spaces
- 2 At #IADIS2025
Automating Data Space Products via Quality Pipelines

Promote

TECNALIA contributes two papers to major conferences in support of PLIADE...

🗨️
🔄
❤️ 1
📊 11
🔖
📤

PLIADES project @PLIADESproject · May 21

📍 Live from Prague!
 Our 4th Plenary Meeting is underway in 🇨🇪, hosted by @PATRIC_expert & @fdcvut

✅ Day 1: WP updates, training, green AI, data security & a magical visit to Strahov Library 📖

✅ Day 2: Sovereign data sharing, cross-domain AI & deployment talks ongoing!

Promote

🗨️
🔄
❤️ 1
📊 29
🔖
📤

Figure 5 Views on the PLIADES posts of X (formerly Twitter)

The image is a screenshot of the YouTube channel homepage for the PLIADES project. At the top, there is a YouTube logo with a 'GR' superscript, a search bar, a microphone icon, and a 'Sign in' button. Below this is a banner image showing a human hand pointing towards a glowing blue robotic hand. The channel name 'PLIADES project' is prominently displayed, along with the handle '@PLIADESproject', 24 subscribers, and 3 videos. A brief description states: 'This is the YouTube channel of PLIADES project. PLIADES is a three and a half years research project fun...more'. Below the description are links to 'pliaDES-project.eu and 2 more links' and a 'Subscribe' button. A navigation bar includes 'Home', 'Videos', and a search icon. The 'Videos' section is active and shows three video thumbnails. The first video is titled 'PLIADES: AI-Powered Data Spaces for a Smarter,...' with 93 views and posted 2 months ago. The second is 'Webinar on International Data Spaces (IDS) Reference...' with 126 views and posted 8 months ago. The third is 'PLIADES project overview' with 104 views and posted 1 year ago.

PLIADES project
@PLIADESproject · 24 subscribers · 3 videos

This is the YouTube channel of PLIADES project. PLIADES is a three and a half years research project fun...more

[pliaDES-project.eu](#) and 2 more links

Subscribe

Home Videos

Videos

PLIADES: AI-Powered Data Spaces for a Smarter,...
93 views · 2 months ago

Webinar on International Data Spaces (IDS) Reference...
126 views · 8 months ago

PLIADES project overview
104 views · 1 year ago

Figure 6 Screenshot of the YouTube channel homepage, showcasing available videos

2.3.3 Press Releases

Press releases remain an important tool in the project's communication strategy, used to formally announce major milestones and introduce the project to a wider audience beyond the immediate stakeholder group.

So far, one official press release has been published. It was issued at the early stage of the project and introduced the PLIADES vision, objectives, and consortium members. It was made available through the project website and shared via social media and partner channels.

Available at: <https://www.pliades-project.eu/media/>

Next Steps:

- Additional press releases are planned for the upcoming months, aligned with key moments such as:
- The publication of new results or deliverables
- The release of Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

2.3.4 Newsletters

The PLIADES newsletter is published twice a year and is one of our main tools for keeping stakeholders informed and engaged. Each issue includes updates on project activities, partner news, upcoming events, and featured content such as videos, use case stories, or publications

Newsletters are shared through:

- Email campaigns to subscribers using the Mailchimp platform.
- Project website, where newsletters are archived for public access in the Media section (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/media/>).
- Social media channels, providing additional outreach and engagement opportunities.

Newsletters Published (M1-M18):

Three issues were published during the first 18 project months.

- **Newsletter #1:** Introduction to the project and roadmap
- **Newsletter #2:** Highlights from the first year and early achievements
- **Newsletter #3:** Focus on the ERF 2025 workshop, participation in Data Week 2025, new project video, recent publications, and the release of the Gender Equality Plan

[PLIADES-Supported Research Wins Best Student Paper Award at ICAART 2025](#)

[PLIADES publishes its Gender Equality Plan to promote inclusive research and innovation](#)

Conference papers

We are proud to announce that two research papers developed within the framework of the PLIADES project have been accepted for presentation at leading international conferences, contributing to the scientific community's understanding of data harmonization and high-quality data products in Data Spaces.

- 📄 Paper 1: "Data Harmonization as a Keystone for IoT-Enabled Data Spaces: Challenges, Techniques, and Future Trends", J. Diaz-de-Arcaya et al.
- 📄 Paper 2: Title: "Towards the Automation of Data Space Products through Quality Data Pipelines", A. Garcia-Perez, R. Miñón, J. Diaz-De-Arcaya, A.I. Torre-Bastida, K. Tsiakas, D. Giakoumis, E. Zulueta-Guerrero

[Read more here](#)

The Future of Data is Here: Watch the PLIADES Project Video

PLIADES Consortium

Meet the PLIADES partners

Follow PLIADES in social

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The current newsletter issue reflects only the view of the author(s) and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Thank you for being part of the PLIADES journey!
The PLIADES Consortium

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Our mailing address is:

[info \[at\] pliaDES-project.eu](mailto:info[at]pliaDES-project.eu)

Want to change how you receive these emails?

You can [update your preferences](#) or [unsubscribe](#)

Figure 7 Newsletter #3

Distribution and Reach

The newsletters have been disseminated to **58 stakeholders** who subscribed through the registration form on the project website. Engagement analytics indicate positive responses, with metrics such as open rates and click-through rates monitored to optimise future issues.

Figure 8 Screenshot of the subscription form available on the PLIADES website

Figure 9 Newsletter #3 distribution and engagement statistics (open rates, clicks) from Mailchimp

Next Steps:

For upcoming issues, we aim to:

- Increase visual content
- Expand the mailing list through event promotion and partner networks
- Offer brief thematic features linked to emerging project results

2.3.5 Short Videos

Short videos have become an important part of the PLIADES communication strategy. They help explain complex ideas in a simple and engaging way, while also giving visibility to key project activities and results.

During the first 18 months of the project, three videos have been produced and published:

- **Project Overview Video** - <https://youtu.be/VZzrUJLq3qo>
A general introduction to the project's goals, concept and expected impact
- **Webinar Recording - International Data Spaces (IDS) Reference Architecture Model** - <https://youtu.be/fiO44bFu1kg>
A recorded session offering insights into one of the project's foundational frameworks
- **PLIADES Promotional Video (released May 2025)** - <https://youtu.be/OkwltOFnXRQ>
A 2.5-minute video presenting the project's vision, objectives, use cases and societal relevance. The entire video - including scriptwriting, narration and editing - was developed internally by the consortium team. It targets a general audience and serves as a concise introduction to what PLIADES is all about.

Figure 10 Screenshot from the PLIADES promotional video

These videos have been shared across the website, social media, and newsletters, and are also used by partners during events and presentations.

Future Video Plans:

- **Content Demonstrations/Workshops:** Videos showcasing demonstrations and workshops related to the project. These will provide practical insights into the project's applications and methodologies, offering a closer look on the PLIADES project.
- **Promo Video on Use Cases:** Promotional videos focusing on use cases. These will highlight the specific use cases within the PLIADES project, showcasing their progress, challenges and successes to illustrate the project's practical impact.
- **Webinars:** Recorded webinars featuring experts and stakeholders discussing various aspects of the PLIADES project. These webinars will provide in-depth information and facilitate knowledge sharing, addressing both technical and non-technical audiences.
- **Recorded Presentations at Workshops/ Conferences:** Recordings of presentations given at various workshops and conferences. These videos will capture key presentations and

insights shared during these events, allowing a broader audience to benefit from the knowledge exchanged.

- **Key Exploitable Results (KERs) Video:** A dedicated video will be created to highlight the KERs of the PLIADES project. This video will focus on the most significant outcomes, demonstrating how these results can be practically applied in various sectors.

2.3.6 Workshops/ Conferences/ Demonstrations

During the first 18 months of the PLIADES project, consortium partners actively participated in a wide range of conferences, exhibitions, webinars, and community events to present the project's vision, technical progress, and early results to diverse audiences. These engagements were key to strengthening the project's visibility, forming new collaborations, and collecting valuable feedback from both academic and industry stakeholders.

Below is a summary of key events attended or co-organised by the PLIADES consortium during M1-M18:

- **DSSC & BDVA Workshop** (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/02/21/pliades-project-bdva-dssc-workshop/>) - 15/02/2024

The PLIADES project participated in a collaborative introductory workshop on data life cycle initiatives, co-organised by the Big Data Value Association (BDVA) and the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC), on 15 February 2024. The online session featured five Horizon Europe projects (under HORIZON-CL4-2023-DATA-01-02)-PLIADES, CycLOps, CEDAR, DS2, and NOUS-sharing their approaches to data value creation and lifecycle management. CERTH, as the coordinator of PLIADES, presented the project's vision, highlighting its contributions toward interoperable and human-centric data spaces. The event offered a valuable opportunity to align with other initiatives, explore synergies, and reinforce the role of PLIADES in the evolving European data ecosystem

- **European Robotics Forum (ERF)** (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VZzrUJLq3qo>) - 22/02/2024

- Held in Rimini, Italy, this event highlighted PLIADES contributions to automation and robotics.
- Partners: CERTH, BOR

- **Talk on "Supporting long-term use of robots and user-friendly Human-Robot Interaction in everyday situations during robot design and development"** (<https://forging-hub.eu/sixth-and-last-edition-of-the-forging-webinar-series-a-focus-on-human-machine-interaction/>) - 01/04/2024

On 1st April 2025, we organised our last edition which focused on human machine interaction innovations. It gathered around 18 participants from different EU countries. The line-up included the following 3 EU experts coming from Denmark, Greece and Spain. They shared best practices and lessons learnt in the field of human machine interaction: Franziska Kirstein (R&D Specialist of Blue Ocean Robotics), Greg Agriopoulos (Co-founder and CEO of Haptikos), Albert Baldo i Canut (CEO of Vaive Logistics)

- **Automation & Robotics Expo** - (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/04/23/pliades-a-r-expo-2024/>) 12-14/04/2024

The inaugural Automation & Robotics Expo, held from April 12 to 14, 2024, at the Athens Metropolitan Expo, in Athens, Greece, showcased over 120 exhibitors presenting cutting-edge solutions spanning AI, drones, Industry 4.0, and robotics. CERTH was among the distinguished participants, presenting the PLIADES project's vision and objectives. This presence highlighted PLIADES' commitment to advancing human-centric data lifecycle solutions within the context of automation and robotics, while fostering connections with industry stakeholders and innovation communities

- **First Webinar on IDS Reference Architecture Model - 19/04/2024**
Organised by the PLIADES consortium, this webinar focused on the International Data Spaces (IDS) framework and how PLIADES integrates these concepts to enable trusted data exchange
- **11th Technology Forum - 25/04/2024**
 - This international forum in Thessaloniki provided an ideal platform to showcase PLIADES' objectives to a diverse audience.
 - Partner: Atlantis Engineering SA
- **Tech Talk | Aligning international standards for data space interoperability (June 2024)**
 - This online event highlighted PLIADES' approach to data space interoperability.
 - Partner: IDSA
- **EUROMAR (Unravelling biological aging: machine learning models for identifying age-related metabolic deterioration from NMR serum data) (30/06 - 04/07 2024)**
 - This scientific conference focused on biological aging and showcased PLIADES-related research to an international scientific audience.
 - Partner: CICbioGUNE
- **ICSR + BioMed Conference (August 2024)**
 - The conference took place in Singapore
 - Partner: BOR
- **88th Thessaloniki International Fair (<https://thessalonikifair.gr/en/visitor-traffic-88th-tif-exceeded-all-expectations>) - 07-15/09/2024**
The 88th Thessaloniki International Fair (TIF), held from 7 to 15 September 2024, in Thessaloniki, Greece, marked a record-breaking edition with over 221,000 visitors and more than 1,300 exhibitors. Among the key participants was CERTH, which hosted a booth to present the vision, objectives, and progress of the PLIADES project. As part of one of Greece's most prominent trade events, CERTH's participation enhanced the visibility of PLIADES, engaging with stakeholders from industry, academia, and the general public, and contributing to the event's strong emphasis on innovation, technology, and international collaboration.
- **European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) - Budapest, Hungary (October 2024)**
 - PLIADES was showcased as part of a session on "Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks"
 - Partner: AVL
- **17th Maintenance Forum - Athens, Greece (October 2024)**
 - This event provided an opportunity for PLIADES to engage with stakeholders from the manufacturing sector.
 - Partner: Atlantis Engineering SA
- **5th Energia. Tec Exhibition - Athens, Greece (October 2024)**
 - PLIADES participated in the exhibition to showcase its contributions to the electromobility sector and entrepreneurs.
 - Partner: Atlantis Engineering SA
- **Connected Motorcycle Consortium Meeting (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/02/11/pliades-innovations-showcased-at-the-connected-motorcycle-consortium/>) - 29/01/2025**
On 29 January 2025, the PLIADES project showcased its latest innovations in Data Spaces applied to Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS), particularly focusing on motorcycles, during the Connected Motorcycle Consortium (CMC) meeting in Bologna, Italy. The event, organised by CMC-a leading non-profit alliance of OEMs, suppliers, researchers, and associations dedicated to integrating Powered Two-Wheelers into future connected mobility systems -attracted a global mix of universities, manufacturers, technology firms, and research centres. Representing the project, the CERTH-Hellenic Institute of Transport (CERTH-HIT) highlighted PLIADES' contributions to rider safety and connectivity in the

two-wheeler domain, reinforcing the importance of data-driven solutions in advancing next-generation mobility.

- **8th Smart Factory Conference (<https://smartfactoryconference.boussiasevents.gr/>) - 18/03/2025**
Representatives from Atlantis Engineering SA joined the 8th Smart Factory conference in Athens, Greece, an event dedicated to technology advancements in manufacturing and in Industry 4.0/5.0 applications. PLIADES' innovations were shared in the field of robotic applications, Machine Learning and automation.
- **European Robotics Forum (ERF) (<https://erf2025.eu/>) 2025 - 27/03/2025**
The PLIADES project organised a dedicated workshop titled "Data Spaces for the Development of AI and Robotic Applications" at the European Robotics Forum (ERF) 2025, held in Stuttgart, Germany, on March 27. The session gathered leading experts to discuss how Data Spaces are shaping the future of AI-driven robotic systems across sectors such as Mobility, Healthcare, and Industry. CERTH was prominently represented by Dr. Dimitrios Giakoumis and Dr. Ioannis Mariolis from CERTH, who presented the PLIADES vision for cross-domain data sharing and the integration of data-driven approaches into robotic applications. The workshop featured contributions from TNO, TalTech, and Blue Ocean Robotics, and highlighted the role of data spaces in enabling smarter, more interoperable and human-centric robotics solutions.
- **European Convergence Summit (ECS) 2025 (<https://adr-association.eu/events/european-convergence-summit-ecs-2025>) - 09/04/2025**
The PLIADES project participated in the European Convergence Summit (ECS) 2025, a high-level event focused on European public policy, digital transformation, and innovation in areas such as Artificial Intelligence, robotics, and big data. Due to venue constraints, projects were represented via digital displays instead of traditional booths. CERTH, as coordinator of PLIADES, contributed a dedicated two-slide presentation that was showcased throughout the event, ensuring visibility among key stakeholders, policy makers, and innovation leaders. Through its presence, PLIADES actively supported the ongoing dialogue around Europe's research priorities and the role of data spaces in enabling next-generation digital services.
- **DSSC TTG Workshop on Data Privacy and Protection (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/06/02/pliades-project-contributes-to-the-dssc-workshop-on-data-privacy-in-data-spaces/>) - 15/05/2025:**
PLIADES, represented by Claudius Laves (THI), participated in the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) Technology Thematic Group (TTG) workshop on data privacy and protection in data spaces. His presentation addressed key security and privacy challenges in cross-sectoral mobility ecosystems, showcasing the PLIADES approach to enabling secure and trustworthy data sharing. The session also featured contributions from TNO, ECSO, SAGE, and TANGO, fostering cross-project dialogue on regulatory and technical enablers.
- **12th Technology Forum (<https://technology-forum.eu/12th-tf-program/>) -16/05/2025**
12th Technology Forum is an IT congress organised in Thessaloniki, Greece focused on innovation, technological advancements, Industry 4.0 applications and entrepreneurship. The event is organised for 11 years and it fosters a collaborative environment for research and industry. This year's conference was focused on the power of data on innovative applications and services. Partners from Atlantis Engineering SA seized the opportunity to share the latest results from the PLIADES project with a vibrant community of innovators, students, and entrepreneurs.
- **Data Week (<https://data-week.eu/>) - 27-28/05/2025**
Data Week 2025, held in Athens, Greece and organised by Big Data Value Association (BDVA), served as a central event for the European Data and AI research and innovation community. CERTH represented the PLIADES project in the collaborative workshop titled "Navigating Challenges and Pioneering Strategies for Data Sharing, Integration and Optimisation and for Leveraging Data Spaces". Kosmas Tsiakas presented on behalf of CERTH, contributing insights

from the PLIADES project alongside other EU-funded initiatives from the Data Spaces Cluster, including Cyclops, DS2, CEDAR, and NOUS. The session focused on stakeholder needs, barriers to data value creation, and real-world data space implementations. PLIADES' participation highlighted its innovative approach to human-centric data sharing and lifecycle optimisation, reinforcing its role in shaping Europe's evolving data ecosystem. By participating in these events, PLIADES continues to build a solid network, establish its reputation in the data space and AI sectors, and ensure its findings reach the target audience effectively.

- **Scientific Conferences - NMR & Health Applications (June 2025)**

CICbioGUNE contributed to three international conferences focused on metabolomics and health, presenting research aligned with PLIADES objectives in biomedical data processing and AI-driven diagnostics.

By participating in these events, PLIADES continues to build a solid network, establish its reputation in the data space and AI sectors, and ensure its findings reach the target audience effectively.

2.3.7 Publications

Scientific publications are a core element of the PLIADES dissemination strategy, helping share the project's findings with the research and industry communities. During the first 18 months, consortium partners contributed to several conferences and events, presenting project technical results.

The following table summarises the publications produced so far:

Table 2 PLIADES Publications

Publication type	Title	Authors	Conference	Partner	Date
Paper in proceedings of a conference	Automated data labelling for pedestrian crossing and not-crossing actions using 3D LiDAR and RGB data	K. Tsiakas, D. Alexiou, D. Giakoumis, A. Gasteratos, D. Tzovaras	2024 IEEE International Conference on Imaging Systems & Techniques (IEEE IST 2024), Tokyo, Japan	CERTH	October. 2024
Poster presentation	Unravelling biological aging: machine learning models for identifying age-related metabolic deterioration from NMR serum data	CICbioGUNE	EUROMAR, Bilbao	CICbioGUNE	30 June - 4 July 2024
Paper in proceedings of a conference	Chain Kode: A CICD methodology for chaincode	Y. R. Witharanage, S. Figueroa-Lorenzo, N.	12th International Conference on Information	Ceit	13-15 December 2024

	development in Hyperledger Fabric based on Kubernetes	Mohammadzadeh, S. Arrizabalaga	Technology: IoT and Smart City (ICIT 2024)		
Paper in proceedings of a conference	An HFB interface for the adoption of blockchain in data spaces	Y. R. Witharanage, S. Figueroa-Lorenzo, S. Arrizabalaga	5th International Conference on IoT, Blockchain & Cloud Computing (IBCOM 2024)	Ceit	16-17 November 2024
Paper in proceedings of a conference	Towards the automation of data space products through quality data pipelines	A. Garcia-Perez, R. Miñón, J. Diaz-De-Arcaya, A.I. Torre-Bastida, K. Tsiakas, D. Giakoumis, E. Zulueta-Guerrero	International Conferences IADIS Information Systems 2025 and e-Society 2025	IADIS, Technalia, CERTH	3 February 2025
Paper in proceedings of a conference	A Novel Vision Transformer for Camera-LiDAR Fusion Based Traffic Object Segmentation	T. Tahves, J. Gu, M. Bellone and , R Sell	17th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence	Taltech	23-25 February 2025
Paper in proceedings of a conference	Glass-box Automated Driving: Insights and Future Trends	M. Bellone, R. Sel and R.-M. Soe	International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence 2025 - ICAART 2025	Taltech	23 February 2025
Paper in proceedings of a conference	Decoding health from NMR spectra: machine learning models for metabolic health	Alain Ibáñez de Opakua, Rubén Gil-Redondo, Maider Bizkarguenaga, Ángela de Diego, Ricardo Conde, Tammo Diercks, Beatriz González-Valle, Nieves Embade, José María Mato, Oscar Millet	Computational Aspects of Biomolecular NMR Gordon Research Conference	CIC bioGUNE Center for Cooperative Research in Biosciences	1-6 June 2025
Paper in proceedings	Data Harmonization	J. Diaz-de-Arcaya, A. Garcia-Perez, L.	10th International	Technalia	19 June 2025

of a conference	as a Keystone for IoT-Enabled Data Spaces: Challenges, Techniques, and Future Trends	Bonilla, R. Miñón, A. I. Torre-Bastida	Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (Splitech 2025)		
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The consortium continues to actively pursue new publication opportunities, particularly as technical components from WP3, WP4, WP6, and WP7 mature and more results are validated. Scientific dissemination will remain a priority throughout the next project period.

The **public deliverables** will be published on the PLIADES web portal as well as on Zenodo community with open access once they are accepted by the EU.

2.3.8 Zenodo Community

The Zenodo community provides an easy-to-use and widely recognised platform for sharing research data, publications, deliverables, software, and multimedia content. It ensures that all PLIADES project materials are stored in a secure, indexed, and accessible way, making it easier for stakeholders to access the latest results, findings, and tools produced throughout the project.

As part of its commitment to open-access dissemination, the PLIADES project has already published a variety of materials on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/pliades-project>). The materials are assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), making them easily discoverable and citable by researchers and stakeholders.

During the first 18 months of the project, the consortium uploaded a variety of materials to the Zenodo community, including:

- The first three project newsletters
- The official project press release
- Visual materials such as the promotional leaflet, poster, and slide deck

In the upcoming period, the repository will be expanded with:

- Additional presentations from conferences and webinars
- Accepted scientific papers and poster contributions
- Public deliverables, once approved by the European Commission

The screenshot displays the Zenodo community interface for the PLIADES project. At the top, the Zenodo logo and search bar are visible, along with navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. The project name 'PLIADES project' and its URL are shown. Below the search results, there are filters for 'Versions', 'Access status', 'Resource types', 'Subjects', and 'File type'. The main content area lists seven items:

- PLIADES Newsletter #3** (June 24, 2025): A newsletter highlighting recent achievements and outreach activities.
- PLIADES Newsletter #2** (December 15, 2024): A newsletter discussing the development of interoperable data spaces and AI-powered solutions.
- PLIADES Newsletter #1** (November 28, 2024): An introductory newsletter providing insights into the project's vision and objectives.
- PLIADES press release - Project overview** (November 28, 2024): A press release introducing the project's vision and innovative approach.
- PLIADES presentation** (November 28, 2024): A slide presentation serving as an open dissemination material.
- PLIADES poster** (November 28, 2024): A poster serving as an open dissemination material.

Figure 11 PLIADES Zenodo community

2.4 Synergies

Synergies play a vital role in maximising the impact and reach of the PLIADES project. By collaborating with other research initiatives, EU-funded projects, and industry partners, PLIADES can amplify its outcomes, share knowledge, and address common challenges in the areas of data spaces, AI integration, and interoperability.

Collaborations with Other EU-funded Projects

Collaborative efforts have been made to establish synergies with other HORIZON-funded projects. These synergies involve exchanging news and social media content, sharing articles for newsletters, and jointly participating in events.

A key synergy effort has been the participation of PLIADES in the **Data Space Cluster**, an informal group of Horizon Europe projects funded under the same call (HORIZON-CL4-2023-DATA-01-02). The cluster includes:

- **DS2²**
- **CEDAR³**
- **CyclOps⁴**
- **NOUS⁵**

Throughout the first 18 months, the projects held **monthly coordination meetings**, during which they discussed technical progress, dissemination actions, and opportunities for joint participation in events. These meetings have strengthened collaboration, ensured message consistency, and allowed sharing of good practices across the projects.

Co-creation of Dissemination Materials:

- Exchange of news items and updates across the cluster projects' communication channels.
- Cross-promotion of events and results via social media and newsletters.
- Shared visibility through coordinated visual materials at events.

Joint Event Participation:

The cluster has co-organised and co-participated in high-visibility events to jointly disseminate their work and connect with broader communities. Notable joint activities include:

- **European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) 2024** (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/10/01/ebdvf-2024/>) - 2-4/10/2024

PLIADES contributed to the discussions on the future of European data spaces and AI-driven ecosystems, as part of the broader cluster presence. Held in Valencia, Spain, EBDVF 2024 gathered a wide array of stakeholders from across Europe, including policymakers, industry leaders, and researchers. The project's participation focused on presenting the human-centric and interoperable data lifecycle frameworks developed within PLIADES, helping to reinforce strategic alignment with European priorities and enhance project visibility at one of the continent's leading data and AI events.

- **Data Week 2025** (<https://data-week.eu/>) - 27-28/05/2025

PLIADES, represented by CERTH, joined the collaborative workshop "Navigating Challenges and Pioneering Strategies for Data Sharing, Integration and Optimisation and for Leveraging Data Spaces" alongside the Data Spaces Cluster projects. The workshop, held in Athens, Greece, brought together key stakeholders to explore practical implementations of data spaces and address technical and organisational barriers. PLIADES highlighted its cross-domain approach in mobility, healthcare, and industry, reinforcing its commitment to human-centric, interoperable data ecosystems.

² www.dataspace2.eu

³ www.cedar-heu-project.eu

⁴ www.cyclopsproject.eu

⁵ www.nous-project.eu

3 Performance Indicators and Monitoring

To evaluate the effectiveness of its dissemination and communication efforts, the PLIADES project uses a set of predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) introduced in the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D8.1). These indicators help measure outreach, engagement, and visibility across digital platforms, media, events, and scientific output.

To track the progress of these KPIs, the PLIADES project uses a combination of analytics tools and regular reports. These include:

- **Website Analytics:** Tools like Google Analytics track visitor data, user interaction, and session duration.
- **Social Media Analytics:** Metrics from LinkedIn, X, and YouTube, such as followers, engagement, and reach.
- **Mailchimp Analytics:** Used for monitoring newsletter distribution and engagement statistics.
- **Event Tracking:** Feedback from events (workshops, conferences) is collected to assess participant satisfaction and engagement.

Below is a summary of the key indicators monitored during the first 18 months of the project, along with progress to date:

Table 3 Key indicators monitored during M1-M18

Dissemination Channels and Activities	KPIs	Targets	Current Status
Project Identity and Branding	Number of branding materials created and distributed.	Logo, colour-space, artboard, graphic visuals	Available online: https://www.pliades-project.eu/media/
Project Website	Website traffic statistics (unique visitors, page views), registrations, blog interactions.	≥700 visits; >120 registrations; ≥150 blog interactions	Website link: https://www.pliades-project.eu Statistics (see section 2.3.1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3.484 sessions • 2.600 unique users.
Marketing Pack and Promotional Press Kit	Number of materials created.	Leaflet, poster, slide-presentations, factsheet	Leaflet/ Poster/ Slide-presentation: See section 2.2 Factsheet: planned for the next period
Web/Social Content (Blogposts, Articles, white papers)	Frequency of content posts.	Year 1: >1/month	14 blogpost/ articles (https://www.pliades-project.eu/news/)
		Year 2: >2/month	11 blogpost/ articles (https://www.pliades-project.eu/news/)
		Year 3: >2/month	-
Social media (LinkedIn, X)	Number of followers, posts, and interactions.	≥200 followers; ≥150 posts; ≥2000 interactions	LinkedIn: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Followers: 220 • Posts: 40 posts • Reactions: 989 X: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Followers: 35 • Posts: 28 posts • Views: 1300 views
		Year 1: ≥4	Press releases: 1

Press Releases, Newsletters, and Digital Briefs	Number of press releases, newsletters, audience reach.		Newsletters: 2
		Year 2: ≥6	Newsletters: 1
		Year 3: ≥10	-
Videos (YouTube Channel)	Number of videos produced, views, and feedback.	1 promo/pilot/tool; total >10 videos	1 promotional video https://youtu.be/OkwltOFnXRQ
Organisation/ Attendance to Conferences/ Workshops	Number of conferences/workshops organised and attended, number of visitors, and speakers.	Organised: ≥2; Attended: ≥15; ≥80 visitors; 10 speakers	Attended: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DSSC & BDVA Workshop - 15/02/2024 • European Robotics Forum (ERF) - 22/02/2024 • Talk on "Supporting long-term use of robots and user-friendly Human-Robot Interaction in everyday situations during robot design and development" - 01/04/2024 • Automation & Robotics Expo - 2-14/04/2024 • First Webinar on IDS Reference Architecture Model - 19/04/2024 • 11th Technology Forum - 25/04/2024 • Tech Talk Aligning international standards for data space interoperability (June 2024) • EUROMAR (Unravelling biological aging: machine learning models for identifying age-related metabolic deterioration from NMR serum data) (30/06 - 04/07 2024) • ICSR + BioMed Conference (August 2024) • 88th Thessaloniki International Fair - 07-15/09/2024 • European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) - Budapest, Hungary (October 2024) • 17th Maintenance Forum - Athens, Greece (October 2024) • 5th Energia.Tec Exhibition - Athens, Greece (October 2024) • Connected Motorcycle Consortium Meeting - 29/01/2025 • 8th Smart Factory Conference - 18/03/2025 • European Robotics Forum (ERF) 2025 - 27/03/2025 • European Convergence Summit (ECS) 2025 - 09/04/2025 • DSSC TTG Workshop on Data Privacy and Protection - 15/05/2025: • 12th Technology Forum -16/05/2025 • Data Week - 27-28/05/2025 • Talk: Decoding health from NMR spectra: machine learning models for metabolic health - 2/6/2025 • Talk: Age and Gender Specific Lipoprotein Characterization for Improved Cardiovascular Risk Stratification - 18/6/2025

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Talk: Metabolomic Insights into Cardiometabolic Health: Bridging the Gap Between Metabolic Dysfunction and Cardiovascular Disease risk (18/6/2025) <p>See sections 2.3.6 and 6</p>
Open Access Exhibitions and Demonstration Events	Number of exhibitions, demo days, and attendees.	≥1 exhibition; ≥2 demo days; ≥100 attendees	Planned for the next period
Onsite Pilot Promotional Demonstrations/ Workshops	Number of demonstrations and workshops per pilot.	≥1 demonstration per pilot; ≥2 workshops per pilot	Planned for the next period
Online and/or F2F Training/ Webinars	Number of webinars/trainings and attendees.	≥2 webinars/trainings; ≥50 attendees	1 webinar (Available online: https://youtu.be/fiO44bFu1kg)
Scientific Publications and Presentations/ Open access reports	Number of journals and conference papers published.	≥5 journals; ≥15 conference papers	8 conference papers (see section 2.3.7). More papers expected in Y2.
Non-Scientific Reports	Number of industry magazine articles.	≥1 industry magazine	-
Project Technical e-Publication	Number of downloads.	<25 = poor; 25-75 = good; >75 = excellent	-
Industry Links and Synergies	Number of real market links, adopters, and trials/testers.	≥10 real market links; ≥5 adopters; ≥5 trials/testers	-
F2F with SMEs and Large Industries/ Companies	Number of events and appearances.	≥1 event; ≥1 appearance	-

To meet these target values, project partners are expected to intensify the communication and dissemination actions in the forthcoming months, putting emphasis on the production of scientific publications, the attendance of external conferences and events as well as the improvement of website visitors and social media followers. As the project is progressing and generating results, more content is being shared with the public, leading to increased outreach to a wider audience.

The performance metrics will continue to be monitored and updated throughout the project to guide improvements and ensure alignment with project goals. A final performance summary will be presented in the last dissemination report (D8.4).

4 Training Programs Design and Development

This section is dedicated to the updates of the design of the training programs for the PLIADES project and reports on activities carried out under Task 8.5. Based on the previous task analysis, three main objectives have been identified for this task: a) design and development of the training programs on security, b) the effective training of the involved parties on the matter of data security and, b) the promotion of the project's results to a wider audience as part of the dissemination activities.

The following units present the results of a survey conducted among consortium partners, aimed at identifying key areas of interest and training needs in the field of data security. It is important that the developed training materials can be publicly shared, as one of the key goals is to offer potential external stakeholders a hands-on introduction to the PLIADES platform and its capabilities. For that reason, the foreseen licensing for the developed components was also investigated during this action.

The survey attempted to specify interesting training topics for the target audiences of the PLIADES training program, in relation to current trends and data security concerns related to cross-domain data spaces, emerging from the implantation of the platform. The final version of the training program is expected by M42.

4.1 Results of the Survey Targeting Internal Stakeholders

The survey was conducted among the PLIADES consortium partners, with participation on a voluntary basis. According to the demographic results, 60% of respondents represented a university or research institute, 30% were from small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and the remaining 10% were affiliated with Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs). Most participants were researchers and technology providers seeking to use the PLIADES Data Spaces either to access data for further technological development or to utilize the software tools and applications available within the PLIADES ecosystem. The sample appears to be a good reflection of the consortium's overall composition, in which approximately 65% identify as universities or research centres and around 21% as SMEs, thereby lending credibility to the survey results.

Most participants self-identified as potential future users of the PLIADES platform, with 60% indicating that they were either owners or contributors of a Key Exploitable Result.

The platform security concerns that were identified during this stage are the following:

1. Injection/usage of unsafe files during data collection
2. Communication breaches between system components
3. Privacy risks in data collection and data sharing
4. Handling of sensitive clinical data
5. Issues related to threat modelling, cryptography, and regulatory compliance
6. General concerns regarding secure data communication

Based on the survey responses, the most preferred training topics to be included in the PLIADES training program are:

1. Regulations related to AI
2. CIA principles (Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability)
3. PLIADES Use Cases

Additionally, topics such as **GDPR** and **Data Spaces onboarding** also received high ratings. The full survey results are presented in Figure 12.

Partners expressed interest in training that covers best practices for **data security** and **protection**, including how to safeguard data and prevent the inference of sensitive information from datasets.

They highlighted the need for guidance on **European AI regulations** and **legal requirements related to data usage**, as well as key considerations for ensuring compliance during data sharing. Additional topics of interest included strategies for enhancing the **security of Data Spaces**, safe handling of human data with a focus on **data integrity** and **access control**, and tailored onboarding processes for both technical and non-technical organizations looking to join a Data Space.

Figure 12 PLIADES training program focus

In response to internal training needs related to data security and compliance, partners highlighted the importance of **understanding GDPR requirements** when handling camera data, managing data storage and access control, and exploring secure data sharing options both within and outside the organization. One partner mentioned ongoing internal efforts focused specifically on data access, while another indicated no current training needs. 60% of the participants expect to have internal training needs regarding data security in the future, but currently they do not have any material already available, and the majority of them are not in the position to provide know-how on the subject. Based on the above, the developed PLIADES training program could be considered an exploitable result, particularly in the area of **knowledge valorisation**.

An important aspect of the training program design, would be the average time available for training, which based on the results, it is typical between 1-5h per month, as presented in the following figure:

Figure 13 Time available for training

As shown in Figure 14, the most preferred training methods are online live courses and pre-recorded online materials, followed by video tutorials and interactive workshops. One partner specifically recommended a blended approach that combines self-study-preferably through written materials-with expert-led workshops, where participants can address specific questions or challenges in a guided setting. Online pre-recorded material was also voted as the most effective way of publishing partners' training material.

Figure 14 Preferred Training Methods

The survey results will guide the organization of the upcoming sections of the training program, which will be developed in parallel with the PLIADES components and aligned with participants' areas of interest. Training material will be created using contributions from task participants and, potentially, from technical partners who provide content related to data security software modules, such as the AI-Connector compliant with IDS standards.

4.2 Training Program Units

Based on the survey's results and an initial analysis to identify Tasks related to data security, a first version of the training program units was created, to be validated within the consortium and task partners, and perhaps enriched with additional offers. An indicative structure is presented in Figure 15:

Training Program Units	Suggested Content
A. Intro to the PLIADES platform	General intro about PLIADES
B. Legislation Security	
B.1 Security Concerns and Gaps	T2.1 Material
B.2 Cross-domain data governance	T3.7 Data Governance
B.3 GDPR Overview & Gaps	T4.7 - Gap analysis assessment & Smart personal identification service
C. Data Security	
C.1 Privacy Preserving Data sharing	T4.3, T5.2 – Cryptographic-encrypted techniques
C.2 Dataspace Secure Onboarding	T5.6 – AI Connectors
C.3 Overview of the EU AI Act	Overview of the legislation related to the use AI for data processing and personalization

Figure 15 Suggested Training Program Units

The comments and feedback gathered will contribute to shaping the first version of the training program structure. While the suggested content aligns well with the training interests identified in the survey, several aspects remain to be defined-such as the format of the training materials (e.g., video, written documents, or presentations).

Training Program Units	Suggested Content
A. Intro to the PLIADES platform	General intro about PLIADES
B. Legislation Security	
B.1 Security Concerns and Gaps	T2.1 Material
B.2 Cross-domain data governance	T3.7 Data Governance
B.3 GDPR Overview & Gaps	T4.7 - Gap analysis assessment & Smart personal identification service
C. Data Security	
C.1 Privacy Preserving Data sharing	T4.3, T5.2 – Cryptographic-encrypted techniques
C.2 Dataspace Secure Onboarding	T5.6 – AI Connectors
C.3 Overview of the EU AI Act	Overview of the legislation related to the use AI for data processing and personalization

Figure 16 Alignment of the training units with the identified training needs

The final, improved version of the training program is expected to be completed by Month 42 (M42) as a key project outcome. This preliminary analysis is anticipated to significantly support and guide the program's development.

5 Conclusions

This report has provided an overview of the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the first 18 months of the PLIADES project. Building upon the early progress made in the first year (D8.2), the consortium has made solid progress in expanding its outreach, increasing visibility, and fostering engagement with stakeholders across multiple channels.

Key achievements include the continuous growth of the PLIADES website and social media presence, the release of targeted newsletters and videos, participation in high-impact events, and the publication of scientific results.

Collaboration within the Data Space Cluster has also proven highly effective, enabling shared visibility and knowledge exchange with related Horizon Europe projects. These synergies will be further developed to support future joint dissemination and exploitation opportunities.

As the project enters its second half, dissemination activities will increasingly highlight emerging results, Key Exploitable Results (KERs), and training opportunities.

Ongoing monitoring of KPIs confirms that the project is on track with its outreach objectives, and the established communication ecosystem is now well-positioned to support broader impact and uptake of PLIADES innovations in the next phase.

6 Appendix

6.1 List of dissemination activities

No	Type of activities	Partners Involved	Title	Date	Place	Type of Audience ('multiple choices' is possible)	Size of audience	Countries addressed	Web links
1	Web	Hypertech	PLIADESprouct started! Kick-off meeting of @HorizonEU @PLIADESprouct at @CERTHell	17/1/2024	X	Followers & visitors	56 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESprouct/status/1747682297703190705
2	Web	Hypertech	In a dynamic two-day kick-off meeting at Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) on 17-18/01, the PLIADES project had a fantastic start! 🚀 Exciting times ahead! 💡 #PLIADES #ResearchProgress #HorizonEurope #research and #innovation programme	19/1/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 768, Clicks: 190, Click through rate (CTR): 24,74%, Likes: 26, Comments: 1, Reposts: 5, Engagement rate: 28,91%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7154108305290801155
3	Web	Hypertech	Exploring Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) facilities, guided by Dimitris Giakoumis and Andreas Kargakos in the context of the kick-off meeting of PLIADES project 🚀 #PLIADESKickOff #researchexcellence	19/1/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 3074, Clicks: 757, Click through rate (CTR): 24,63%, Likes: 62, Comments: 1, Reposts: 7, Engagement rate: 26,90%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7154128802573410305
4	Web	Hypertech	In a dynamic two-day kick-off meeting at @CERTHell on 17-18/01, the PLIADES project had a fantastic start! 🚀 Exciting times ahead! 💡 #PLIADES #ResearchProgress	19/1/2024	X	Followers & visitors	65 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESprouct/status/1748343681101213967

5	Web	Hypertech	<p>✍️ Exciting news! #PLIADES project showcased at the recent workshop organised by the BDVA - Big Data Value Association and the Data Spaces Support Centre focusing on Horizon Europe Projects in Data Life Cycles. Dr. Dimitris Giakoumis, our Coordinator from Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH), had the honour of presenting our project's mission and objectives to a diverse audience, including members of BDVA's Task Force on Data Spaces and representatives from DSSC.</p> <p>This event provided a crucial platform for us and four other Horizon Europe projects to discuss our goals and anticipated impacts, particularly regarding Data Sharing in the Common EU Data Spaces.</p> <p>Stay tuned for more updates on our journey!</p> <p>Check more out more: https://lnkd.in/dVXRrF2C</p>	21/1/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	<p>Impressions: 447, Clicks: 42, Click through rate (CTR): 9,40%, Likes: 22, Comments: 0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 15,21%</p>	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7166046219369234434
6	Web	Hypertech	<p>PLIADES Project Launch: Kick-off Meeting in Thessaloniki, Greece</p>	7/2/2024	Online	Website's visitors	44 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/02/07/pliades-project-launch-kick-off-meeting-in-thessaloniki-greece/
7	Web	Whire Research	<p>Mention of Kick-off of the PLIADES project meeting in the January edition of White Research Journal</p>	9/2/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	<p>Impressions: 547, Clicks: 25, Click through rate (CTR): 4,57%, Likes: 20, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 8,59%</p>	International	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/welcome-january-edition-our-company-newsletter-white-research-sprl-igl0f/?trackingId=fS2RTDaS2S8HzkBukeCzDg%3D%3D
8	Workshops	CERTH	<p>BDVA-DSSC Workshop: An online workshop organised by the Big Data Value Association and Data Spaces Support Centre, focusing on data spaces, where the project was introduced to relevant stakeholders.</p>	19/2/2024	Online	Scientific, industry		International	

9	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES project presented at BDVA and DSSC Workshop on Horizon Europe Projects in Data Life Cycles	21/2/2024	Online	Website's visitors	57 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/02/21/pliades-project-bdva-dssc-workshop/
10	Web	Hypertech	✍️ Exciting news! #PLIADES showcased at @BDVA_EU and DSSC Workshop on Horizon Europe Projects in #DataLifeCycles. Our coordinator, Dr. Dimitrios Giakoumis highlighted our commitment to advancing European data strategies. #HorizonEurope Learn more: https://t.co/q1ckX35nKj	21/2/2024	X	Followers & visitors	66 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1760278496738148496
11	Videos	CERTH	European Robotics Forum, Project Overview	22/2/2024	Online	Scientific, industry		International	https://youtu.be/VZrUJLq3qo
12	Web	ZERO	Repost of the PLIADES announcement for the Big Data Value Association (BDVA) and Data Space Support Center (DSSC)	26/2/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors		International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7167807982448197632
13	Web	Whire Research	Article on WR's website for PLIADES project	February 2024	Online	Website's visitors	Impressions: 411, Clicks: 20, Click through rate (CTR): 4,87%,	International	https://white-research.eu/portfolio/pliades-ai-enabled-data-lifecycles-optimization-and-data-spaces-integration-for-increased-efficiency-and-interoperability/
14	Web	Whire Research	Social media post on WR's account about the Kick off meeting held in Thessaloniki	February 2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 1080, Clicks: 369, Click through rate (CTR): 34,17%, Likes: 38, Comments: 0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 38,06%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/white-research-sprl-ai-efficiency-security-activity-7155880751815667712-YzEA?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
15	Conferences	BOR	European Robotics Forum	March 2024	Rimini, Italy	Scientific, industry	20	European countries	
16	Presentations	BOR	Talk on "Supporting long-term use of robots and user-friendly Human-Robot Interaction in everyday situations during robot design and development."	1/4/2024	Online Workshop	Research, Scientific, Industry	30	European countries	https://forging-hub.eu/sixth-and-last-edition-of-the-forging-webinar-series-a-focus-on-human-machine-interaction/
17	Exhibitions	Hypertech	A&R Expo 2024	12-14/04/2024	Athens, Greece	Industry, Researchers, Entrepreneurs, Innovators	With over 120 exhibitors from Greece		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/04/23/pliades-a-r-expo-2024/

							and abroad, the A&R Expo showcased cutting-edge technological solutions spanning a wide spectrum, from Artificial Intelligence applications to innovative drone technologies. Attendees were treated to a diverse array of products and services tailored to meet industrial and professional demands, reflecting Greece's steadfast commitment to technological advancement .		
18	Other	IDSA	Webinar on International Data Spaces (IDS) Reference Architecture Model	19/4/2024	Online			International	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fiO44bFu1kg
19	Web	Hypertech	Exciting News from A&R Expo 2024! 🇬🇷 The recent Automation & Robotics Expo in Athens from April 12th to 14th, 2024, showcased the latest innovations in the field. Among the 120+ exhibitors was the Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH), proudly presenting PLIADES'	23/4/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 288, Clicks: 28, Click through rate (CTR): 9,72%, Likes:12, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 14,24%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7188520794107297792

			vision and objectives. For more information, check here: https://lnkd.in/dJttaiG						
20	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES at the A&R Expo 2024	23/4/2024	Online	Website's visitors	43 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/04/23/pliades-a-r-expo-2024/
21	Conferences	Atlantis Engineering SA	11th Technology Forum	25/4/2024	Thessaloniki, Greece	Industry, Researchers, Entrepreneurs, Innovators	100 (approx.)	International event	https://technology-forum.eu/
22	Web	ZERO	Announcement of ZERO going to the GA meeting in Graz	27/4/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors		International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7264924466374135809/?actorCompanyId=70051986
23	Web	Hypertech	🔗 Exciting News from A&R Expo 2024! @CERTHellas proudly showcasing #PLIADES' vision and objectives in the recent Automation & Robotics Expo in Athens from April 12th to 14th, 2024 Show more here: https://t.co/Br1F3zQaNI	30/4/2024	X	Followers & visitors	47 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESpject/status/1785279115601289345
24	Web	Whire Research	Social media post on WR's account about the 2nd project meeting held in Bilbao	May 2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	538	International	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/white-research-sprl_the-pliades-project-recently-gathered-activity-7207314221481549825-V4fM?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
25	Web	Hypertech	🔗 We're excited to announce that the first press release for the #PLIADESpject is now live on our website! 📄 Read the press release here: https://lnkd.in/dAXBCdhj #PressRelease #Innovation #Research #Collaboration	17/5/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 411, Clicks: 20, Click through rate (CTR): 4,87%, Likes:11, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 7,79%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7197245987801698304
26	Web	Hypertech	Revolutionising Data Utilisation Across Sectors	17/5/2024	Online	Website's visitors	36 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/05/17/the-pliades-project/
27	Web	Hypertech	Exciting News! The first press release for the #PLIADESpject is now available on our website! 📄 Read it here: https://t.co/TVL9I4ZYg6	17/5/2024	X	Followers & visitors	48 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESpject/status/1791480938838307320
28	Web	Hypertech	👂 The PLIADES team is meeting today at the AIC - Automotive Intelligence Center to discuss our project progress. Stay tuned for updates on our achievements and outcomes and	29/5/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 1080, Clicks: 369, Click through rate (CTR): 34,17%, Likes:	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7201565063126618113

			don't forget to visit our website for more → https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq #PLIADESproject #Innovation #Research #Collaboration #HorizonEurope #DataLifeCycles #DataIntegration				38, Comments: 0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 38,06%		
29	Web	Hypertech	👁️ The #PLIADES team is meeting today at the AIC - Automotive Intelligence Center to discuss our project progress. Stay tuned for updates on our achievements and outcomes and don't forget to visit our website for more → https://pliades-project.eu	29/5/2024	X	Followers & visitors	190 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1795814735608418586
30	Web	Hypertech	👁️ The second day of the PLIADES project is still in progress! Big thanks to Innovalia Association for the fantastic hosting at the AIC-Automotive Intelligence Center. #Innovation #Collaboration #PLIADESproject #Innovation #Research #Collaboration #HorizonEurope #DataLifeCycles #DataIntegration	30/5/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 937, Clicks: 352, Click through rate (CTR): 37,57%, Likes: 43, Comments: 0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 42,58%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7201920999854862336
31	Web	Hypertech	👁️ The second day of the PLIADES project is still in progress! Thanks to @Innovalia_group for the fantastic hosting at the AIC-Automotive Intelligence Center.	30/5/2024	X	Followers & visitors	62 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1796155637786648695
32	Web	Hypertech	🚀 Exciting News! 🚀 We are introducing the Ethics Advisory Board of the #PLIADES project! This dedicated team will ensure that our R&D activities uphold the highest ethical standards. 👥 Meet our esteemed members: Gabriela B., Javier Del Ser, Andrej Pastorek, Prof. Ondrej Pribyl, Jesus M. Santamaria and sofia segkouli. Their expertise is pivotal to our success and ethical integrity.	7/6/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 547, Clicks: 25, Click through rate (CTR): 4,57%, Likes: 20, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 8,59%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7204774947053907968

			Learn more: https://lnkd.in/dmrbw-tT #Ethics #HorizonEurope #Innovation #AI #DataProtection #DataLifeCycles #DataIntegration						
33	Web	Hypertech	Introducing the PLIADES project's Ethics Advisory Board	7/6/2024	Online	Website's visitors	48 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/06/11/second-plenary-meeting-of-the-pliades-project-key-highlights-and-progress/
34	Web	Hypertech	Meet our experts https://t.co/oPgD0rmcd5	7/6/2024	X	Followers & visitors	48 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESPROJECT/status/1799009937429078121
35	Fair	CERTH	Thessaloniki International Fair	07-15/9/2024	Thessaloniki, Greece	Industry, Researchers, Entrepreneurs, Innovators			
36	Web	Hypertech	Stay updated: https://lnkd.in/dPyM3rjy #PLIADES #HorizonEurope #Innovation #AI #DataInnovation #DataLifeCycles #DataIntegration	11/6/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 961, Clicks: 67, Click through rate (CTR): 6,97%, Likes: 26, Comments: 0, Reposts: 5, Engagement rate: 10,20%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206210971621634048
37	Web	Hypertech	Second Plenary Meeting of the PLIADES Project: Key Highlights and Progress	11/6/2024	Online	Website's visitors	84 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/06/11/second-plenary-meeting-of-the-pliades-project-key-highlights-and-progress/
38	Web	Hypertech	Exciting progress at the 2nd #PLIADES plenary meeting! From WP updates to demos and a visit to @Innovalia_group premises, we're advancing AI-driven data sharing.	11/6/2024	X	Followers & visitors	98 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESPROJECT/status/1800447630168011014

			Next stop: Graz, Austria! 📌 Stay updated: https://t.co/9QhMq5JofL						
39	Other	IDSA	Tech Talk Aligning international standards for data space interoperability	13/6/2024	Online	Research, Scientific, Industry	40	International event	
40	Web	Whire Research	Mention of 2nd PLIADES project meeting in the summer edition of White Research Journal	31/7/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	576	International	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/white-research-journal-summer-2024-edition-white-research-sprl-nlvhf/?trackingId=RM3nPGVkrZOnTkTgi5rGuQ%3D%3D
41	Conferences	BOR	ICSR + BioMed	August 2024	Singapore	Scientific	40	Singapore, China	
42	Web	Hypertech	🎉 Excited to announce that PLIADES with Bernhard Peischl (AVL) will join @DS2_EU 's session with @nous_project, @CyclopsProject & @cedar_eu at @BDVA_eu 2024! Topic: Interoperability of data spaces for seamless value creation	1/10/2024	X	Followers & visitors	43 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1841143355675160986
43	Web	Hypertech	🎉 We are excited to announce that PLIADES project, with Bernhard Peischl from AVL, will be participating in the joint session led by DS2, alongside our sister projects NOUS, CyclopsProject and CEDAR EU at this year's BDVA - Big Data Value Association #EBDVF2024! Interoperability of data spaces for seamless value creation networks 📅 2 October 🕒 10 AM CET 📍 Budapest, Hungary Learn more about the session 📌 https://lnkd.in/dKRpSi64	1/10/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 451, Clicks: 24, Click through rate (CTR): 5,32%, Likes: 15, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 8,87%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7246908755597049856
44	Web	Hypertech	Unlock the Power of Data Sharing at EBDVF 2024: Enhancing Value Creation Through Interoperable Data Spaces	1/10/2024	Online	Website's visitors	27 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/10/01/ebdvf-2024/
45	Presentations; Conferences	AVL	Session title: "Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks", European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)	2/10/2024	Budapest, Hungary	Industry; Researchers; Innovators; Policy makers		EU	

46	Conferences	Atlantis Engineering SA	17th Maintenance Forum	10/10/2024	Athens, Greece	Industry	150	Greece, EU	https://www.maintenance-forum.gr/
47	Exhibitions	Atlantis Engineering SA	5th Energia.Tec	11-13/10/2024	Athens, Greece	Industry	300	Greece, EU	https://www.energia-tec.gr/en/
48	Web	Hypertech		23/10/2024	X	Followers & visitors	77 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1849053168388182194
49	Web	Hypertech	Missed it? Watch the full recording here: https://lnkd.in/dJ9DdiXt #IDS #IDA_RAM #DataSpaces #DigitalTransformation #PLIADES #Interoperability #webinar #IDSA	23/10/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 298, Clicks: 17, Click through rate (CTR): 5,70%, Likes: 14, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 10,74%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7257343445332058112
50	Web	Hypertech	On the 2nd of October, Bernhard Peischl from AVL proudly represented the PLIADES project at this significant event in Budapest. The session, led by DS2 and attended by our sister projects: NOUS, CyclopsProject and CEDAR EU, delved deep into critical topics like data lifecycle management, AI-driven services and human-centred	23/10/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 625, Clicks: 146, Click through rate (CTR): 23,36%, Likes: 29, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2,	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7254816772254539778

			integration within data spaces We explored how data interoperability can drive value creation across sectors, helping unlock new opportunities for businesses and society. Want to know more about the outcomes? Visit https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq for updates! #DataSpaces #Interoperability #AI #BigData #Innovation #EBDVF2024				Engagement rate: 28,32%		
51	Web	Hypertech	Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks - A Great Success at EBDVF 2024!	23/10/2024	Online	Website's visitors	26 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/10/23/ebdvf-2024-avl/
52	Web	Hypertech		30/10/2024	X	Followers & visitors	38 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESpject/status/1851579474510283105
53	Web	Hypertech	Insights from the PLIADES Webinar on International Data Spaces Reference Architecture (IDS-RAM)	30/10/2024	Online	Website's visitors	34 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/10/30/ids-ram-webinar/
54	Web	Hypertech	The #PLIADES team is gearing up for the 3rd Plenary Meeting in Graz, Austria AT from Nov 19-21! We're excited to drive forward #DataSpaces & #AI innovations with sessions, updates, and our WP4 Hackathon for hands-on, collaborative solutions! https://t.co/RnE4DQkFU0	14/11/2024	X	Followers & visitors	43 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESpject/status/1857033449502126309

55	Web	Hypertech	<p>📍 The 3rd Plenary Meeting of the PLIADES project is set to take place in Graz, Austria, from November 19th to 21st! Hosted by AVL, this gathering will showcase critical updates on all project Work Packages (WPs).</p> <p>🔑 Key Event: The WP4 Hackathon will give attendees a hands-on experience with the systems PLIADES is developing. Participants will work in mixed remote and on-site teams to brainstorm solutions, focusing on IDS RAM and connector development.</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/d_VwmTKu</p> <p>#PLIADESProject #DataSpaces #AI #DataInnovation #GrazMeeting #DataLifeCycles #DataIntegration #HorizonEurope</p>	14/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 370, Clicks: 19, Click through rate (CTR): 5,14%, Likes: 17, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 10,00%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7262798525460062210
56	Web	Hypertech	<p>Countdown to the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting in Graz</p>	14/11/2024	Online	Website's visitors	17 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/11/14/3rd-plenary-announcement-graz/
57	Web	Hypertech	<p>✉️ The first issue of the #PLIADESProject newsletter is out!</p> <p>Catch the latest updates on our journey to transform #AI & #DataSpaces in mobility, healthcare & more.</p> <p>📖 Read now: https://mailchi.mp/bc644c5be18f/pliades-newsletter-1</p> <p>🔗 Not subscribed? Sign up at https://pliades-project.eu</p>	15/11/2024	X	Followers & visitors	19 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1857369422727377004
58	Web	Hypertech	<p>✉️ The first issue of the PLIADES newsletter is out!</p> <p>Discover the latest updates from the PLIADES project, our objectives, milestones, and exciting highlights</p>	15/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 427, Clicks: 26, Click through rate (CTR): 6,09%, Likes: 18,	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7263133975429201920

			<p>from the initial months of our journey toward revolutionising data utilisation across mobility, healthcare, manufacturing and energy sectors.</p> <p> Sign up in moments: Scroll to the footer of our website and click "Sign up" to the newsletter: https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq</p> <p>#PLIADESProject #HorizonEurope #AI #DataSpaces #Innovation #Newsletter</p>				Comments: 0, Reposts: 3, Engagement rate: 11,01%		
59	Web	Hypertech	<p> https://pliaDES-project.eu/news/</p>	19/11/2024	X	Followers & visitors	29 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1858882620446089661
60	Web	Hypertech	<p> Key Highlights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress reviews across several Work Packages (WPs), ensuring alignment with our goals. 	19/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 1483, Clicks: 343, Click through rate (CTR): 23,13%, Likes: 57, Comments: 0, Reposts: 8, Engagement rate: 27,51%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7264647133859901441

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The much-anticipated #Hackathon Session is now underway, uniting remote and on-site participants to collaborate on IDS RAM and connector development- a true testament to innovation and teamwork! <p>With an excellent start, we're looking forward to more engaging discussions and activities in the coming days! 🚀</p> <p>📧 Subscribe to our newsletter to stay in the loop & receive all the latest updates, event news, and opportunities to be involved. Scroll to the footer of our website and click "Sign up" to the newsletter: https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq</p> <p>#PLIADESProject #DataSpaces #AI #Collaboration #Innovation</p> <p>DS2 NOUS CEDAR EU CyclopsProject</p>						
61	Web	AVL	<p>Repost of the PLIADES announcement for Day 1 of the 3rd PLIADES project Plenary Meeting in Graz hosted by AVL.</p>	19/11/2024	LinkedIn	Industry, Researchers, Entrepreneurs, Innovators		International	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/pliades-project_hackathon-pliadesproject-dataspaces-ugcPost-7264647130600853504-0sei?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACBMQLYBKMyJZcTjWcYs_wvK3RVR_hhC4ZA
62	Web	Hypertech	<p>🗨️ Day 2 of the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting - Building on Progress and Exploring Innovations!</p> <p>The second day of our meeting continues with an engaging agenda, focusing on technical advancements and collaboration. This morning, we delved deep into WP4: Green and Decentralized Data Storage and Security, with detailed updates on WP tasks. 🌍 📄</p> <p>We also reviewed WP8: Dissemination, Exploitation, and</p>	20/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	<p>Impressions: 1416, Clicks: 388, Click through rate (CTR): 27,40%, Likes: 46, Comments: 0, Reposts: 8, Engagement rate: 31,21%</p>	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7264976290858876929

			<p>Standardization, highlighting progress on dissemination activities, the exploitation plan, and training programs - key steps toward impactful outcomes. 🌱</p> <p>📅 The program now shifts to Technical Workshops, exploring our innovative Use Cases.</p> <p>As we wrap up the day, we eagerly await the exciting visit to AVL premises for an immersive look into their state-of-the-art facilities. 🚀</p> <p>The momentum continues as the PLIADES project moves towards its vision of advancing data spaces, AI, and green solutions!</p> <p>#PLIADESProject #DataSpaces #AI #Collaboration #Innovation #HorizonEurope</p> <p>DS2 NOUS CEDAR EU CyclopsProject</p>						
63	Web	Hypertech	<p>🚀 A dynamic period for the PLIADES project! ATLANTIS Engineering SA proudly represented PLIADES innovations at both the 17th Maintenance Forum and the 5th Energia.Tec exhibition.</p> <p>At the Maintenance Forum, Atlantis showcased PLIADES' AI solutions that enhance interoperability across diverse dataspace. Meanwhile, at Energia.Tec, Atlantis showcased PLIADES cutting-edge advancements in dataspace technology.</p> <p>Read more: https://lnkd.in/d7CcNt4U</p> <p>More to come as we lead the way in data-driven solutions!</p>	25/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	<p>Impressions: 262, Clicks: 28, Click through rate (CTR): 10,69%, Likes: 21, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 19,47%</p>	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7266794234584682497

			#PLIADESproject #Innovation #Dataspaces #AI #IndustrialMaintenance #EnergyTechnology #HorizonEurope DS2 NOUS CEDAR EU CyclopsProject						
64	Web	Hypertech	Atlantis Engineering showcases PLIADES innovations at the 17th Maintenance Forum and 5th Energia.Tec	25/11/2024	Online	Website's visitors	42 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/11/25/atlantis-participations-october2024/
65	Web	Hypertech	📌 @DS2_EU leads the release of the new report "Enhancing Value Creation Through Interoperable Data Spaces" with @PLIADESproject, @cedar_eu, @CyclopsProject and @nous_project, showcasing insights from the Data Spaces Cluster at BDVA EBDVF 2024. https://t.co/L1xlAM6j8V	29/11/2024	X	Followers & visitors	24 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1862499754447368599
66	Web	Hypertech	📄 New Report Released! We are thrilled to announce the release of "Enhancing Value Creation Through Interoperable Data Spaces" a report led by DS2 in collaboration with PLIADES project, CEDAR EU, CyclopsProject and NOUS. This report highlights the key takeaways from the Data Spaces Cluster participation at the BDVA EBDVF 2024 in October 2024. The report encapsulates the discussions from the panel session "Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks" Read the full report here: 🌐 https://lnkd.in/d_3AujET 📧 Sign up in moments: Scroll to the footer of our website and click "Sign up" to the newsletter:	29/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 359, Clicks: 12, Click through rate (CTR): 3,34%, Likes: 20, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 9,47%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7268264394990473216

			https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq #EUOpenData #Dataspaces #Innovation #PLIADESproject #DataSpacesCluster #Interoperability #HorizonEurope DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject PLIADES project NOUS						
67	Web	Hypertech	Enhancing Value Creation Through Interoperable Data Spaces: Insights from the Data Spaces Cluster Report	29/11/2024	Online	Website's visitors	24 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/11/29/ebdvf-data-spaces-cluster-report/
68	Web	AVL	Highlights from the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting in Graz, Austria 🚗 Last week, the PLIADES project partners gathered to share updates and insights on our journey toward advancing Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM Association), validating Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS), and exploring innovations in Human-Robot Interaction (HRI). By leveraging cutting-edge data and services, PLIADES is at the forefront of driving the future of industrial data sharing in Europe. Thank you to everyone who presented, contributed, and collaborated. 🤝 #AI #innovation #collaboration	29/11/2024	LinkedIn	Industry, Researchers, Entrepreneurs, Innovators	Impressions: 7,549 Engagement: 883 (Sum of likes, comments and shares) Reactions: 91 Reposts: 10 CTR: 10,3 % (Click Through Rate) ER: 11,7 % (Engagement Rate)	International	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/avl_ai-innovation-collaboration-ugcPost-7268277540362801153-p4D9?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACBMQLYBKMyJZcTjWcYs_vwK3RVR_hhC4ZA
69	Web	AVL	Highlights from the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting in Graz, Austria 🚗 Last week, the PLIADES project partners gathered to share updates and insights on our journey toward advancing Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM Association), validating Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS), and exploring innovations in Human-Robot Interaction (HRI). By leveraging cutting-edge data and services, PLIADES is at the forefront of driving the future of industrial data sharing in	29/11/2024	Facebook	Industry, Researchers, Entrepreneurs, Innovators	Impressions: 6.577 Interactions: 36 (sum of likes, comments and shares)	International	

			Europe. Thank you to everyone who presented, contributed, and collaborated. 🤝 #AI #innovation #collaboration						
70	Web	Hypertech	<p>📢 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting Recap!</p> <p>Over 50 participants from 27 partner organisations gathered in Graz, Austria AT for a 3-day event packed with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Progress Updates ◆ Use Case Workshops ◆ Hackathon session 🌀 ◆ AVL Facility Tour <p>📧 For more: https://t.co/KtzOWCaYqz</p>	9/12/2024	X	Followers & visitors	26 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1866100498425864268
71	Web	Hypertech	<p>📝 Reflecting on the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting! 📝</p> <p>From 19-21 November 2024, over 50 project members from 27 partner organisations gathered in Graz, Austria, for the 3rd Plenary Meeting of the PLIADES Project, hosted by AVL. This critical gathering of partners drove the project closer to its 12th-month milestone and was packed with technical insights and collaborative problem-solving.</p> <p>Key Highlights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ Progress Updates: Status of major deliverables and next steps. ✅ Use Case Workshops: Alignment on data flow integration and technical testing. ✅ Hackathon Success: WP4 Hackathon led by Energy@Work, CEIT, and TNO, enabling participants to collaborate on IDS RAM and connector development ✅ Tour of AVL Facilities: A unique 	9/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 398, Clicks: 29, Click through rate (CTR): 7,29%, Likes: 19, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 12,31%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7271864193732005889

			<p>opportunity to explore partner contributions on-site.</p> <p>This 3-day meeting showcased the power of collaboration, innovation, and shared ambition. As we approach our M12 milestone, the team remains committed to driving forward the next generation of AI-enabled data spaces.</p> <p>#PLIADES #DataSpaces #AI #Innovation #Collaboration #PlenaryMeeting #GreenData #DigitalTransformation #HorizonEurope</p> <p>DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS</p>						
72	Web	Hypertech	<p>PLIADES 3rd Plenary Meeting: Milestones Reached, Next Steps Defined</p>	9/12/2024	Online	Website's visitors	66 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/12/09/3rd-plenary-meeting-highlights/
73	Web	Hypertech	<p>📧 The 2nd issue of the #PLIADES newsletter is coming soon! 📄 Don't miss out - sign up now! 📍 Scroll to the footer of our website & click "Sign up": https://pliades-project.eu</p> <p>#Innovation #Research #Newsletter</p>	10/12/2024	X	Followers & visitors	28 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1866431769840628057
74	Web	Hypertech	<p>🚀 Our Sister Project DS2 Needs Your Feedback! 🚀 The DS2 project from the Data Space Cluster is running a quick survey on B2B data sharing, and your insights are essential! 📝 By participating, you'll help shape the future of data spaces and open data initiatives.</p> <p>Let's support DS2 and strengthen the #EUOpenData, #Dataspaces, and #Datauration community!</p>	10/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 89, Clicks: 11, Click through rate (CTR): 12,36%, Likes: 4, Comments: 0, Reposts: 0, Engagement rate: 16,85%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272230541033168896
75	Web	Hypertech	<p>🚀 The 2nd issue of the PLIADES newsletter is on its way! 🚀 Don't miss out on the latest project</p>	10/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 141, Clicks: 13, Click	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272184314631450624

			<p>updates, key highlights, and exclusive insights from recent activities, including our successful 3rd Plenary Meeting in Graz!</p> <p>🔗 Not a subscriber yet? Stay ahead of the curve and join our growing community.</p> <p>📧 Sign up is quick and easy - scroll to the footer of our website and click "Sign up" to the newsletter: https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq</p> <p>Be the first to know - subscribe today!</p> <p>#PLIADES #Newsletter #Innovation #Research #StayInformed #HorizonEurope</p> <p>DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS</p>				through rate (CTR): 9,22%, Likes: 7, Comments: 0, Reposts: 0, Engagement rate: 14,18%		
76	Web	Hypertech	<p>📄 New Publication!</p> <p>We're excited to announce PLIADES's first #conference #paper: "Automated Data Labelling for Pedestrian Crossing and Not-Crossing Actions Using 3D LiDAR and RGB Data", presented at the 2024 IEEE IST Conference in Tokyo.</p> <p>📖 Read more: https://t.co/pPKBsU7ZgV</p>	11/12/2024	X	Followers & visitors	27 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESPROJECT/status/1866782035731419628
77	Web	Hypertech	<p>📄 New Publication Alert!</p> <p>We are thrilled to announce the publication of PLIADES project first conference paper: "Automated Data Labelling for Pedestrian Crossing and Not-Crossing Actions Using 3D LiDAR and RGB Data".</p> <p>This innovative paper, co-authored by Kosmas Tsiakas, Dimitris Alexiou, Dimitris Giakoumis, Antonis Gasteratos, and Dimitrios Tzouvaras, was presented at the 2024 IEEE</p>	11/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 424, Clicks: 35, Click through rate (CTR): 8,25%, Likes: 20, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 13,44%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272542608164278272

			International Conference on Imaging Systems and Techniques (IST) in Tokyo, Japan. Read more here: https://lnkd.in/d59J9_e2 #PLIADES #DataSpaces #AI #Innovation #HorizonEurope #Pedestrians #Annotations #Tracking #Roads #Pipelines #Neural_networks #Autonomous_vehicles DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS						
78	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES unveils first conference paper on Automated Data Labelling for Pedestrian Crossing and Not-Crossing Actions Using 3D LiDAR and RGB Data	11/12/2024	Online	Website's visitors	64 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/12/11/pliades-conference-paper-on-automated-data-labelling/
79	Web	Hypertech	Read more here: https://lnkd.in/d59J9_e2 #PLIADES #DataSpaces #AI #Innovation #HorizonEurope #Pedestrians	11/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 608, Clicks: 36, Click through rate (CTR): 5,92%, Likes: 24, Comments:0, Reposts: 22, Engagement rate: 10,20%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272542608164278272

			#Annotations #Tracking #Roads #Pipelines #Neural_networks #Autonomous_vehicles DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS						
80	Web	Hypertech	📣 The 2nd PLIADES Newsletter is Out! 📣 Don't miss key updates & milestones: 🌟 IDS-RAM Webinar insights 🌟 EBDVF 2024 showcase 🌟 Partner activities & research 📖 Read it here: https://pliaDES-project.eu/media/ 📧 Subscribe at the bottom of our website!	13/12/2024	X	Followers & visitors	69 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1867508567370006629
81	Web	Hypertech	📣 The 2nd Issue of the PLIADES Newsletter is Out! 📣 Discover the latest updates, key milestones, and major achievements from the past few months, including: 🌟 Highlights from the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting 🌟 Insights from the PLIADES Webinar on IDS-RAM 🌟 PLIADES at EBDVF 2024 🌟 Partner Activities & New Research 📖 Read the 2nd issue now: https://lnkd.in/dakByjbr 📧 Don't miss future updates! Subscribe at the bottom of our website to receive the latest news straight to your inbox. https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq #PLIADES #Newsletter #DataSpaces #Innovation #AI #Interoperability #HorizonEurope	13/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 126, Clicks: 15, Click through rate (CTR): 11,90%, Likes: 11, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 22,22%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7273273418056163328

			DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS						
82	Web	Hypertech	<p>📧 The 2nd Issue of the PLIADES Newsletter is Out! 📧 Discover the latest updates, key milestones, and major achievements from the past few months, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🌟 Highlights from the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting 🌟 Insights from the PLIADES Webinar on IDS-RAM 🌟 PLIADES at EBDVF 2024 🌟 Partner Activities & New Research <p>👉 Read the 2nd issue now: https://lnkd.in/dakByjbr</p> <p>📧 Don't miss future updates! Subscribe at the bottom of our website to receive the latest news straight to your inbox. https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq</p> <p>#PLIADES #Newsletter #DataSpaces #Innovation #AI #Interoperability #HorizonEurope</p>	13/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 259, Clicks: 19, Click through rate (CTR): 7,34%, Likes: 12, Comments:0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 12,74%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7273273418056163328
83	Presentations	CERTH	The innovations of Pliades EU project in Dataspaces and its applications to Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) and especially on motorcycles were presented during the meeting of the Connected Motorcycle Consortium at Bologna Italy on 29th of January 2025 with worldwide participation from Universities, Manufacturers, Technology Companies and Research Centres.	29/1/2025	Bologna, Italy				
84	Web	Hypertech	🌟 We are thrilled to announce the publication of the PLIADES Gender Equality Plan (GEP)! 🌟🌟	3/2/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 333, Clicks: 15, Click	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7292193878219120641

			<p>Developed as part of our commitment to diversity, equity, and inclusion 🌍, the GEP outlines actions to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ Promote gender balance in recruitment and leadership ✅ Address gender bias in AI systems ✅ Integrate gender-sensitive approaches in research & data governance ✅ Foster inclusive participation across project activities <p>Aligned with the EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, the GEP supports PLIADES in creating an ethical, responsible, and inclusive research environment.</p> <p>📄 Read the full plan here: https://lnkd.in/gduNNESW</p>				through rate (CTR): 4,50%, Likes: 20, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 10,81%		
85	Web	Hypertech	<p>📢 Exciting news! The PLIADES Gender Equality Plan (GEP) is out! 🌍👩🏫</p> <p>It drives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ Gender balance in recruitment & leadership ✅ Bias-free AI systems ✅ Gender-sensitive research & data governance ✅ Inclusive participation <p>📄 Read more: https://t.co/VLawr0u9i8</p>	3/2/2025	X	Followers & visitors	25 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESPROJECT/status/1886439161269198873
86	Web	Hypertech	<p>PLIADES publishes its Gender Equality Plan to promote inclusive research and innovation</p>	3/2/2025	Online	Website's visitors	43 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/02/03/pliades-gender-equality-plan/
87	Web	Hypertech	<p>👉 We Need Your Feedback! 👈</p> <p>The PLIADES project is conducting a survey to capture human factors that affect the data lifecycle and will contribute to identifying security</p>	6/2/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 239, Clicks: 5, Click through rate (CTR): 2,09%, Likes: 8, Comments:	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7293263629863325696

			specifications and requirements for the PLIADES framework. Your insights are invaluable and the survey lasts less than 12 minutes. #PLIADES #AI #DataSpaces #HorizonEurope #Humanfactors #HFA				0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 7,11%		
88	Web	Hypertech		6/2/2025	X	Followers & visitors	36 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1887501775021670709
89	Web	Hypertech	We Need Your Feedback! Contribute to PLIADES Survey on Human Factors in the Data Lifecycle	6/2/2025	Online	Website's visitors	8 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/02/06/survey-humanfactors/
90	Web	Hypertech	 On 29 January 2025, the PLIADES	11/2/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 233, Clicks: 10, Click through rate (CTR): 4,29%,	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7295077351980175360

			<p>project presented its cutting-edge advancements in Dataspaces and their applications to Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) - focusing on motorcycles - at the Connected Motorcycle Consortium meeting in Bologna, Italy.</p> <p>📍 Stay tuned for more updates on how PLIADES is shaping the future of mobility!</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/dCjm9H9d</p> <p>#CITS #MotorcycleSafety #DataSpaces #ConnectedMobility #ResearchInnovation #HorizonEurope</p>				Likes: 11, Comments: 0, Reposts: 0, Engagement rate: 9,01%		
91	Web	Hypertech	<p>🔔 Reminder! The PLIADES project survey on human factors in the data lifecycle is still open!</p> <p>🚀 Your insights will help shape security specifications for the PLIADES framework. It only takes 12 minutes to complete!</p> <p>Thank you for your valuable input! 🙏</p> <p>DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS #AI #DataSpaces #HorizonEurope #Humanfactors #HFA</p>	11/2/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 207, Clicks: 12, Click through rate (CTR): 5,80%, Likes: 10, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 11,11%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7294996828188508160
92	Web	Hypertech	<p>PLIADES innovations showcased at the Connected Motorcycle Consortium</p>	11/2/2025	Online	Website's visitors	22 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/02/11/pliades-innovations-showcased-at-the-connected-motorcycle-consortium/
93	Web	Hypertech	<p>🔔 Survey Deadline Extended! 🔔</p> <p>Thank you to everyone who has already completed the PLIADES survey! 🙏</p> <p>The deadline has been extended until 17 February 2025. If you haven't shared your insights yet, there's still time! Your input will help us identify human factors that impact the data</p>	14/2/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 131, Clicks: 3, Click through rate (CTR): 2,29%, Likes: 6, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 8,40%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296098245376696320

			lifecycle and shape security specifications for the PLIADES framework. 📌 Take the survey now: https://lnkd.in/dNneWftW Your feedback is invaluable - thank you for contributing! #PLIADES #AI #DataSpaces #HumanFactors #HorizonEurope						
94	Conferences	Taltech	17th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence (ICAART 2025)	22-24/02/2025	Porto, Portugal				
95	Web	Hypertech	📌 PLIADES-Supported Research Wins Best Student Paper Award at ICAART 2025! 🏆 We are thrilled to share that the paper "A Novel Vision Transformer for Camera-LiDAR Fusion based Traffic Object Segmentation" has been awarded the Best Student Paper Award at the 17th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence (ICAART 2025) in Porto, Portugal! 📌 Speaker & Award Winner: Toomas Tahves (PhD Researcher) 📄 Authors: Toomas Tahves, Jun-Yi Gu, PhD, Mauro Bellone, Raivo Sell 👤 Supervisors: Prof. Raivo Sell & Dr. Mauro Bellone This paper, partially supported by the PLIADES project, introduces the Camera-LiDAR Fusion Transformer (CLFT)-a novel deep learning model that integrates vision transformers with multimodal sensor fusion to enhance traffic object segmentation. The research contributes to advancing AI-driven perception for autonomous vehicles, improving classification across diverse categories such as cyclists, traffic	7/3/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 347, Clicks: 17, Click through rate (CTR): 4,90%, Likes: 18, Comments: 0, Reposts: 0, Engagement rate: 10,09%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7303735919994454018

			signs, and pedestrians, while also adapting to various weather conditions. Congratulations to the entire team for this remarkable achievement! #ICAART2025 #AI #ComputerVision #AutonomousDriving #VisionTransformers #LiDAR #DeepLearning #ResearchExcellence #AwardWinningResearch #PLIADES #FinEst #SmartCities #Innovation #AutonomousVehicles https://lnkd.in/dw-pcyUM						
96	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES-Supported Research Wins Best Student Paper Award at ICAART 2025	7/3/2025	Online	Website's visitors	36 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/03/07/pliades-award-icaart2025/
97	Workshops	ZERO	Presentation and Q&A session about a Semi-Autonomous Vehicle-Following system in the "Mensch-in-Bewegung" workshop series (>1h). A significant portion of the presentation focused on PLIADES and data spaces.	11/3/2025	Online Workshop	Interested Audience			https://mensch-in-bewegung.info/event/vortragsreihe-nachhaltiges-modernes-leben-plant-ein-konzept-fuer-die-mobilitaet-der-zukunft/
98	Web	Hypertech	🚀 Join us at #ERF2025 for the @PLIADESproject Workshop! 📅 27 March 🕒 11:10 📍 Room 20, Stuttgart 💡 Topic: Data Spaces for AI & Robotics 📣 Don't miss it! 🌐 https://pliades-project.eu/erf2025-pliades-workshop/	12/3/2025	X	Followers & visitors	21views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1899769588939722932
99	Web	Hypertech	🚀 Join us at ERF 2025 for an exclusive PLIADES project Workshop! 📍 The European Robotics Forum #ERF2025 is coming to Stuttgart, Germany, from 25-27 March, bringing	12/3/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 705, Clicks: 25, Click through rate (CTR): 3,55%, Likes: 20,	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7305534287649370113

			<p>together top robotics and AI experts. As part of this event, we are excited to host Workshop Session No. 43 - Data Spaces for the Development of AI and Robotic Applications.</p> <p> Franziska Kirstein (Blue Ocean Robotics) - End-user perspective in 			<p>Comments: 0, Reposts: 6, Engagement rate: 7,23%</p>	
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			<p>Healthcare</p> <p>📢 Don't miss out! Join us to explore how Data Spaces are shaping the future of AI & Robotics.</p> <p>🌐 Learn more: https://lnkd.in/dj_Zv7hh</p> <p>🗣️ Let's shape the future of AI & Robotics together! #ERF2025 #PLIADES #Data, #AI, #DataSpace, #Mobility, #Healthcare, #Industry</p> <p>DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS</p>						
100	Web	Hypertech	<p>Join the PLIADES Workshop at ERF 2025: Unlocking the Potential of Data Spaces in AI & Robotics</p>	12/3/2025	Online	Website's visitors	85 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/03/12/erf2025-pliades-workshop/
101	Conferences	Atlantis Engineering SA	<p>8th Smart Factory Conference</p>	18/3/2025	Athens, Greece	Industry		Greece, EU	https://smartfactoryconference.boussiasevents.gr/
102	Web	Hypertech	<p>🚀 Join us at #ERF2025 for the PLIADES project Workshop! 🚀 The European Robotics Forum (ERF) 2025 is coming to Stuttgart, Germany, from 25-27 March, bringing together top robotics and AI experts. Don't miss Workshop Session No. 43 - Data Spaces for AI & Robotics, where we explore how Data Spaces drive secure, interoperable, and federated data sharing!</p> <p>📢 Be part of the conversation! 🌐 More Info: https://lnkd.in/dj_Zv7hh</p> <p>🗣️ Let's shape the future of AI & Robotics together! #ERF2025 #PLIADES #AI #Robotics #DataSpaces</p>	21/3/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 353, Clicks: 15, Click through rate (CTR): 4,25%, Likes: 17, Comments: 0, Reposts: 3, Engagement rate: 9,92%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7308781127094145025
103	Web	Hypertech	<p>🚀 One Day Left! Join the PLIADES project #Workshop at #ERF2025! 🚀</p> <p>🗣️ Meet the Experts Shaping the Future of AI, Robotics & Data Spaces!</p>	26/3/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 677, Clicks: 28, Click through rate (CTR): 4,14%,	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7310579896576049152

			<p> Meet Our Esteemed Speakers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Matthijs Punter (TNO) - Insights and introduction to Data Spaces ◆ Dr. Dimitris Giakoumis (CERTH-ITI) - Data Spaces for Mobility, Healthcare and Industrial domains ◆ Erik Cornelisse (TNO) - Data Space Protocol in Energy, Smart Industry, and Healthcare ◆ Dr. Ioannis Mariolis (CERTH-ITI) - Data Spaces for the development of robotics: the PLIADES paradigm ◆ Dr. Mauro Bellone (FinEst centre, Taltech) - End-user perspective in Mobility ◆ Franziska Kirstein (Blue Ocean Robotics) - End-user perspective in Healthcare <p>#ERF2025 #PLIADES #Data #AI #DataSpace #Mobility #Healthcare #Industry</p> <p>DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS</p>			Likes: 23, Comments: 0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 8,12%	
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104	Workshops	CERTH, BOR, TNO, Taltech	Workshop Session No. 43 titled "Data Spaces for the Development of AI and Robotic Applications" during the European Robotics Forum 2025 (ERF2025)	27/3/2025	Stuttgart, Germany				https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/05/06/pliades-workshop-at-erf2025-a-successful-discussion-on-the-role-of-data-spaces-in-ai-robotics/
105	Web	Hypertech	<p>👉 Help our sister project, DS2, shape the future of intelligent chatbots! 🤖</p> <p>Share your thoughts in the survey below!</p>	27/3/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 107, Clicks: 4, Click through rate (CTR): 3,74, Likes: 2, Comments: 0, Reposts: 0, Engagement rate: 5,61%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7311007895481942017
106	Presentations	CERTH	<p>European Convergence Summit (ECS) 2025</p> <p>The PLIADES project participated in the European Convergence Summit (ECS) 2025, a high-level, one-day, face-to-face event dedicated to European public policies and innovation. The Summit brought together a wide range of experts, policy makers and stakeholders to discuss and converge on key research directions for Europe, with a particular focus on Artificial Intelligence, robotics and big data innovation.</p> <p>Due to space limitations at the venue, it was not possible to organise a traditional project exhibition with booths or posters. Instead, projects were invited to contribute with a short visual presence. PLIADES was represented through a dedicated two-slide presentation, which was displayed on screens throughout the venue in a continuous loop during the event. This format enabled visibility alongside other research and innovation projects from the second wave of partnerships launched in 2023-2024.</p>	9/4/2025	Online			International	

			Through its presence, PLIADES contributed to the broader dialogue on digital transformation and innovation in Europe and ensured the project's key messages and objectives were visible to a diverse and influential audience.						
107	Web	Hypertech	<p>🔊 The future of data is smart, secure & sustainable. Discover how #PLIADES integrates AI & #DataSpaces for real-world impact in mobility, health, industry & energy.</p> <p>📺 Watch the official video: https://youtu.be/OkwltOFnXRQ</p> <p>#HorizonEurope</p>	25/4/2025	X	Followers & visitors	19 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1915678017080225823
108	Web	Hypertech	<p>🔊 The future of data is here - and it's intelligent, secure and connected.</p> <p>We're excited to share the official video of the PLIADES project, showcasing how we optimise data lifecycles and enable cross-sector AI-powered collaboration through integrated Data Spaces. From safer autonomous mobility and personalised healthcare to sustainable manufacturing and energy systems, PLIADES is building the AI-driven foundation for tomorrow's innovations.</p> <p>📺 Watch the video to explore how our framework supports real-world use cases https://lnkd.in/dRv9kzFt</p> <p>#AI #DataSpaces #HorizonEurope #SmartMobility #DigitalHealth #Industry40 #Sustainability #HumanRobotInteraction #PLIADES</p> <p>DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS</p>	25/4/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 396, Clicks: 29, Click through rate (CTR): 7,32%, Likes: 19, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 12,37%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7321440486047514624

109	Web	Hypertech	The Future of Data is Here: Watch the PLIADES Project Video	25/4/2025	Online	Website's visitors	10 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/04/25/the-future-of-data-is-here-watch-the-pliades-project-video/
110	Web	Hypertech	<p>🔗 PLIADES was present at the 8th Smart Factory Conference in Athens - a key event focused on Industry 4.0 and 5.0 technologies!</p> <p>Our partner ATLANTIS Engineering SA Engineering had the opportunity to showcase PLIADES project innovations in robotic applications, machine learning and automation in manufacturing. It was an inspiring space to connect with other frontrunners in IoT, AI and smart manufacturing.</p> <p>🚀 We're proud to contribute to the future of European industry through the PLIADES project!</p> <p>#PLIADESproject #SmartFactory2025 #Industry40 #Industry50 #AI #Robotics #SmartManufacturing #HorizonEurope</p>	30/4/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 677, Clicks: 24, Click through rate (CTR): 3,55%, Likes: 18, Comments: 1, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 6,50%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7323312563344015360
111	Web	Hypertech	<p>Great to be at the 8th Smart Factory Conference in Athens!</p> <p>🔗 @EngAtlantis shared @PLIADESproject innovations in robotics, ML and automation 🤖 Inspiring discussions on #IoT #AI #Industry40 and #SmartManufacturing!</p> <p>#SmartFactory2025 #HorizonEU #Industry50</p>	30/4/2025	X	Followers & visitors	21 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1917550258915025084
112	Web	ZERO	Announcement of the official PLIADES video	30/4/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors		International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7323313798784737280
113	Web	Hypertech	<p>🔗 PLIADES Workshop at ERF2025: A Deep Dive into Data Spaces for AI & Robotics</p> <p>Workshop Session No. 43, organised by the PLIADES project, took place at the European Robotics Forum (ERF2025) in Stuttgart and gathered</p>	6/5/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 311, Clicks: 14, Click through rate (CTR): 4,50%, Likes: 19, Comments: 0, Reposts: 0,	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7325496980489560065

			<p>over 50 participants from research, industry and policy sectors. The session focused on the critical role of data spaces in enabling secure and interoperable AI-driven robotics in mobility, healthcare, and industry.</p> <p>📁 Access all presentations: https://lnkd.in/dzJrDgez</p> <p>#AI #DataSpaces #HorizonEurope #SmartMobility #DigitalHealth #Industry40 #Sustainability #PLIADES</p> <p>DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS</p>				Engagement rate: 10,61%		
114	Web	Hypertech	<p>PLIADES Workshop at ERF2025 - A Successful Discussion on the Role of Data Spaces in AI & Robotics</p>	6/5/2025	Online	Website's visitors	48 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/05/06/pliades-workshop-at-erf2025-a-successful-discussion-on-the-role-of-data-spaces-in-ai-robotics/
115	Web	Atlantis Engineering SA	<p>Twitter post about 17th Maintenance Forum</p>	11/5/2025	X	Followers & page visitors	3 reposts, 4 Likes, 67 Views	International	<p>(1) ATLANTIS Engineering on X: "Honored to present the PLIADES project's tech advances at the 17th Maintenance Forum! Our AI solutions for improving interoperability across diverse dataspace brought a fresh perspective to the discussion. See you next year! https://t.co/QldjsNU7SK @EngAtlantis @PLIADESproject https://t.co/G6SEchoekM" /X</p>
116	Workshops	THI - Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt	<p>DSSC Workshop on Data Privacy in Data Spaces</p> <p>On 15 May 2025, the PLIADES project proudly participated in the DSSC Technology Thematic Group (TTG) workshop on Data Privacy and Protection in Data Spaces. Organised online via Microsoft Teams, the workshop brought together experts from leading data space initiatives to explore critical topics related to privacy, security and the future of trustworthy data sharing.</p> <p>Claudius Laves (Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt) represented the PLIADES project, contributing a dedicated presentation on Security and privacy issues related to data</p>	15/5/2025	Online			International	

			spaces. His input highlighted the challenges and proposed solutions that the PLIADES project is addressing, particularly regarding secure, privacy-respecting data exchange in cross-sectorial mobility ecosystems. The agenda featured keynote interventions by Freek Bomhof (TNO) and Roberto Cascella (ECSO), as well as insights from the Green Deal Data Space SAGE and the TANGO project. A lively discussion followed, encouraging collaboration across communities of practice and strategic support facilities.						
117	Conferences	Atlantis Engineering SA	12th Technology Forum (https://technology-forum.eu/): IT congress focused on innovation, technological advancements, Industry 4.0 applications and entrepreneurship. The event is organised for 11 years and it fosters a collaborative environment for research and industry.	16/5/2025	Thessaloniki, Greece	Researchers, scientific community, start-ups founders, investors, professors, companies, entrepreneurs, innovators	> 300	International event	https://technology-forum.eu/
118	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES at Data Week 2025: Advancing Data Sharing and Data Space Strategies	16/5/2025	Online	Website's visitors	49 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/05/16/pliades-at-data-week-2025-advancing-data-sharing-and-data-space-strategies/
119	Web	Hypertech	✈️ PLIADES is heading to #DataWeek2025 in Athens! Join us on May 27 (14:00-15:30 EEST) for a collaborative workshop on navigating challenges and strategies in Data Sharing & Data Spaces. Together with CyclopsProject, DS2, CEDAR EU, and NOUS, we'll explore: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☑ Stakeholder needs and expectations ☑ Barriers to data value creation ☑ Innovative, real-world solutions 	16/5/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 314, Clicks: 13, Click through rate (CTR): 4,14%, Likes: 10, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 7,64%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7329071633275547648

			Learn more: https://lnkd.in/de8bMvap Let's build the future of interoperable, human-centric data ecosystems! #PLIADES #DataSpaces #HorizonEurope #AI #Innovation #DataValue #BDVA #DataWeek25 #Datasharing							
120	Web	Hypertech	With @CyclopsProject, @DS2_EU, @cedar_eu, @nous_project Details: t.co/GzgZ0b1SFp	16/5/2025	X	Followers & page visitors	32 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1923308345508634692	
121	Web	Atlantis Engineering SA	LinkedIn Post about Technology Forum	18/5/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & page visitors	669 Impressions, 47 Likes	International	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/mariapapaspyropoulou_technologyforum2025-pliers-innovation-activity-7329871158667796480-rrdD?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAADLPfR4BFT3LeLlsgwtgNOhi3v-wVo9Tn4M	
122	Web	Atlantis Engineering SA	Twitter post about 12th Technology Forum	18/5/2025	X	Followers & page visitors		International	https://t.co/Fx8Bzh4GyL / X (1) Maria Papaspyropoulou on X: "Another inspiring #TechnologyForum comes to an end! 🎉 Honored to be part of the 12th edition and to share @PLIADESproject results with young innovators and entrepreneurs from across Greece and beyond. See you next year! 🌟 #Innovation #DataScience #Thessaloniki @EngAtlantis"	
123	Web	Hypertech	The 4th Plenary Meeting of the PLIADES project is underway in Prague, from 20-21 May 2025.	21/5/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 2038, Clicks: 567, Click	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7330882292766208000	

			<p>The meeting is hosted by #PATRIC Prague Advanced Technology and Research Innovation Center, a.s. and the Czech Technical University in Prague (Fakulta dopravní ČVUT v Praze)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Day 1 included work package updates, training sessions and a guided visit to the Strahov Library. ◆ Day 2 continues with presentations on AI-enabled data sharing, cross-domain interoperability and deployment planning. <p>#AI #DataSpaces #Interoperability #PlenaryMeeting #CVUT #PATRIC #HorizonEurope</p>				through rate (CTR): 7,82%, Likes: 86, Comments: 0, Reposts: 16, Engagement rate: 32,83%		
124	Web	Hypertech	<p>📍 Live from Prague! Our 4th Plenary Meeting is underway in cz, hosted by @PATRIC_expert & @fdcvut</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☑ Day 1: WP updates, training, green AI, data security & a magical visit to Strahov Library 📺 ☑ Day 2: Sovereign data sharing, cross-domain AI & deployment talks ongoing! 	21/5/2025	X	Followers & page visitors	27views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESPROJECT/status/1925118615742710039
125	Web	Hypertech	<p>🗨️ Just one day to go! Don't miss tomorrow's engaging session at #DataWeek2025 in Athens!</p> <p>We're proud to share that our Project Coordinator Dimitris Giakoumis and Kosmas Tsiakas from the Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) will represent PLIADES project in the collaborative workshop on Data Sharing & Data Spaces.</p> <p>📅 27 May 2025 🕒 14:00 - 15:30 EEST 📍 OTE Group of Companies (HTO), Athens</p>	26/5/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 191, Clicks: 13, Click through rate (CTR): 6,81%, Likes: 9, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 12,04%	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7332668191497781248

			<p>Alongside projects CyclopsProject, DS2, CEDAR EU, and NOUS, they will contribute to the discussion on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Stakeholder needs & expectations ✓ Barriers to data value creation ✓ Real-world, human-centric data solutions <p>📍 Full event info: https://lnkd.in/de8bMvap</p> <p>Come join the conversation and help shape the future of interoperable and trustworthy data ecosystems!</p> <p>#PLIADES #HorizonEurope #DataSpaces #DataSharing #Innovation #AI #BDVA #DataValue #DataWeek25 #DigitalTransformation</p> <p>CyclopsProject DS2 CEDAR EU NOUS</p>						
126	Workshops	CERTH	DataWeek, "Workshop Title: Navigating Challenges and Pioneering Strategies for Data Sharing, Integration and Optimisation and for Leveraging Data Spaces"	27/5/2025	Athens, Greece				https://data-week.eu/session/value-creation-in-data-spaces-2/
127	Conferences	CICbioGUNE	Talk: Decoding health from NMR spectra: machine learning models for metabolic health Conference: Computational Aspects of Biomolecular NMR Gordon Research Conference	2/6/2025	Les Diablerets (Switzerland)	Research, Scientific, Industry	150	International	https://www.grc.org/computational-aspects-of-biomolecular-nmr-conference/2025/
128	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES Project Contributes to the DSSC Workshop on Data Privacy in Data Spaces	2/6/2025	Online	Website's visitors	20 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/06/02/pliades-project-contributes-to-the-dssc-workshop-on-data-privacy-in-data-spaces/
129	Web	Hypertech	📢 Exciting news from the PLIADES project! On 15 May 2025, Claudius Laves from the Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt presented at the Data Spaces Support Centre Technology Thematic Group Workshop on Data Privacy and	2/6/2025	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 174, Clicks: 7, Click through rate (CTR): 4,02%, Likes: 9, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1,	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7335325257274130435

			<p>Protection in Data Spaces. His presentation focused on security and privacy issues in data spaces, showcasing PLIADES project insights and progress in this rapidly evolving domain. 🛡️💡</p> <p>The workshop also featured experts from TNO, ECSO, Green Deal Data Space SAGE and TANGO, sparking valuable discussions about Privacy Enhancing Technologies, cybersecurity, and the future of trusted data sharing in Europe.</p> <p>🙌 A big thank you to the organisers and contributors for this insightful event!</p> <p>#PLIADES #DataSpaces #CyberSecurity #PrivacyEnhancingTechnologies #HorizonEurope #MobilityInnovation #DSSC #THI</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/dfkZk-XY</p>				Engagement rate: 9,77%		
130	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES Showcases Vision for European Digital Innovation at the European Convergence Summit 2025	17/6/2025	Online	Website's visitors	5 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/06/17/pliades-showcases-vision-for-european-digital-innovation-at-the-european-convergence-summit-2025/
131	Conferences	CICbioGUNE	<p>Talk: Age and Gender Specific Lipoprotein Characterization for Improved Cardiovascular Risk Stratification</p> <p>Conference: NMR metabolomics symposium</p>	18/6/2025	Nantes (France)	Research, Scientific, Industry	100	European countries	https://nmrmetabo.sciencesconf.org/
132	Conferences	CICbioGUNE	<p>Talk: Metabolomic Insights into Cardiometabolic Health: Bridging the Gap Between Metabolic Dysfunction and Cardiovascular Disease risk</p> <p>Conference: NMR metabolomics symposium</p>	18/6/2025	Nantes (France)	Research, Scientific, Industry	100	European countries	https://nmrmetabo.sciencesconf.org/
133	Web	Hypertech	TECNALIA contributes two papers to major conferences in support of PLIADES research on data spaces	24/6/2025	Online	Website's visitors	19 views	International	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2025/06/24/tecnalia-contributes-two-papers-to-major-conferences-in-support-of-pliades-research-on-data-spaces/
134	Web	Hypertech	📌 @PLIADESproject highlights from @tecnalia:	24/6/2025	X	Followers & page visitors	10 views	International	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1937452095881322549

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📄 2 papers accepted! 📄 At #SpliTech2025 📄 Data Harmonization as a Keystone for IoT-Enabled Data Spaces 📄 At #IADIS2025 📄 Automating Data Space Products via Quality Pipelines 						
135	Posters	CICbioGUNE	Unraveling biological aging: machine learning models for identifying age-related metabolic deterioration from NMR serum data	30/06 - 04/07 2024	EUROMAR. Bilbao	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	700	International (~100)	
136	Web	Atlantis Engineering SA	Twitter post about Smart Factory event	4/8/2025	X	Followers & page visitors	4 reposts, 5 likes, 96 views	International	(1) ATLANTIS Engineering on X: "It was a great opportunity to attend the 8th Smart Factory Conference in Athens! @EngAtlantis Atlantis was there to witness all the cutting-edge innovations in IoT, AI, robotics, smart manufacturing and share the @PLIADEsproject initiatives #SmartFactory2025 #Industry40 https://t.co/IRXRcjpVBA" / X
137	Web	Atlantis Engineering SA	Twitter post about Energia Tec event	11/12/2025	X	Followers & page visitors	1 repost, 3 Likes, 63 Views	International	(1) ATLANTIS Engineering on X: "The @PLIADEsproject participated in the 5th Energia.Tec, an international exhibition focused on energy technology and E-mobility, to showcase its cutting-edge innovations in dataspace technology. Find out more: https://t.co/IgAqPiBckx #dataspaces#emobility#energy https://t.co/qZ0IscRPLt" / X